

ANIMAL POETICS: AN EXPLORATION INTO ETHICAL
INTERSPECIES PERFORMANCE-MAKING

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Abstract

The purpose of this project is to uncover how an animal can be represented ethically on stage as a co-performer. I aim to understand animal ethics in the context of performance through a theoretical investigation that engages with select journals, books, web pages and articles. Through contextualising the human-animal relationship, stemming from prehistory, primary examples of animal representation showcase how humankind portrays animals in social, cultural and global settings, framing this towards an implied morality of relations present in religious scripture that bonds humans to animals through a moral responsibility.

Analysing animal ethics theoretically identifies speciesism as a key factor in the unjust treatment of nonhumans due to their species group, where 'otherness' is introduced as a term to understand the differing moral standing animals possess as moral patients; a perspective that can be questioned through identifying the importance of animal morality to examine animals as sentient subjects rather than objects. We find that consideration of animal morality can be highlighted throughout the speciesism debate, showcasing that ethical concerns for nonhumans must always be placed at the forefront, regardless of speciesist or anti-speciesist attitudes.

As a representative example of animal ethics in the context of performance, Kira O'Reilly's pig work presents practical insight into how to eliminate the notion of animal 'otherness', enabling ethical animal representation on stage to emerge through the removal of human agency. We discover in an ethics of attentiveness that truly *seeing* the animal beyond representation as a sign system plays a crucial role in avoiding anthropocentric performance-making approaches, enabling spectators to be affected by the performing animal on stage through a rejection of speciesism that perceives performance through the lens of a nonhuman subject. This project contributes towards an understanding of how ethics, care and relation can combine to ensure that ethical animal representation on stage is framed in a morality of relations to nonhumans that challenges anthropocentrism.

Statement & Declaration

To uncover how an animal can be represented ethically on stage as a co-performer, the research objectives are as follows:

1. Contextualise the human-animal relationship and examples of animal representation since prehistory to introduce a morality of relations that bonds humans to animals through a moral responsibility.
2. Challenge speciesism and the notion of animal 'otherness' to blur the human-animal distinction through interrogating animal morality and humanity's relationship with itself.
3. Analyse the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker and spectator of interspecies performance to demonstrate ethics as a poetics that rejects speciesism and questions anthropocentric perspectives.
4. Provide Kira O'Reilly's creative practice and approach as a representative example to understand how animal ethics, care and relation combine to represent a nonhuman ethically on stage.

This research will use a selection of literature collected from books, online articles, online journals and web pages, as listed in the appropriate bibliography¹, to conduct all findings in the objectives listed above. This thesis has been assisted closely by Dr Eve Katsourkai as lead supervisor and Dr Steve Collins as secondary supervisor.

I declare that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree or comparable academic award, such as a DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

¹ Bibliography is listed on Page. 76.

Ethics & Plagiarism

Ethical Considerations (No Participants)

This study did not involve the use of Human Participants in the collection of data. There was, therefore, no application made for ethical approval to the Module Coordinator.

Plagiarism Statement

I confirm that by signing, dating and submitting this thesis, I have read, understood and accepted the University's regulations in relation to Cheating and Plagiarism.

Signed Sophie Grubb

Name Sophie Grubb

Date 29/09/2025

Introduction

Animal Poetics: An Exploration into Ethical Interspecies Performance-Making is a theoretical investigation of animal ethics on stage. This study aims to understand how animal ethics work in the context of performance. My key research question that guides this investigation is to determine how an animal can be represented ethically on stage as a co-performer. When I discuss 'representation', I am referring to the portrayal, specifically of animals, in a particular way. For example, the section 'Animals as Food' in Chapter One refers to humankind establishing nonhumans as a resource, thus portraying and representing them as objects for human consumption. Ethical animal representation on stage implies the nonhuman has been portrayed as an equal co-collaborator alongside a human counterpart, where theoretically analysing animal ethics aids in determining how this can be achieved. To do so, I draw on theories and findings from philosophers, animal studies scholars, books, journals, online web pages and articles.

I present theatre artist Kira O'Reilly's interspecies work as a representative example of how care and ethics can combine to portray and ultimately represent a nonhuman as a co-performer alongside a human on stage. I analyse two of O'Reilly's interspecies pig works later in my thesis; however, this project is not an analysis of O'Reilly's lengthy engagement with animals in her interspecies work. Rather, her work highlights the key points of my exploration of interspecies poetics². There are other examples of interspecies work that I could have drawn on within this project, such as Matthew Herbert's *One Pig* (2011), where he showcases live audiences an audio soundscape that captures a swine's environment over 25 weeks before slaughter. Additionally, Tarsh Bates's *in vitro* (2011) explores the human-animal relationship where audiences are invited to care for nine nonhuman organisms in an art gallery. However, due to certain limitations regarding word count and time period, O'Reilly's work showcases a clear poetics of interspecies performance-making.

² 'Poetics' is detailed in Chapter Three.

The theatre is a space that can serve as a powerful tool for change and function as a mirror of society, investigating and representing real-life issues back to audiences. Steve Collins and Nii Kwaterlai Quartey (2023) explain:

Ever since the development of performance spaces in ancient Greece, sites of performance have served specific functions in communities, providing a space for an audience to enter and view a world or time that is reflective of, but not, their own (p. 125).

The stage may be an artificial space; however, very real contemporary social, cultural and global issues can be examined through performance. The focus of my work is to identify the connection between humans and animals from the Paleolithic era to determine the tacit moral responsibility humans have to animals, inscribed within religious scriptures such as the Bible and the Dhammapada. The morality of relations between humans and animals provides a term that emphasises an ethical principle regarding humanity's interconnectedness to animals. O'Reilly provides a practical insight into how she highlights these principles and showcases them within her interspecies work on stage.

To break down my project, Chapter One traces the history of the human-animal relationship throughout the three main periods of prehistory: the Paleolithic, Mesolithic and Neolithic. Contextualising a timeline of animal portrayal throughout the centuries enables me to uncover the various representations that humanity placed on nonhumans, such as hunters, clothing, shelter and domesticates. This wide frame narrows to animals on stage, specifically the representation of nonhumans as entertainers.

I provide a broad timeline of animal representation over the years to suggest that humanity has abandoned its implied moral responsibility to care for animals, introducing this morality of relations between them. Highlighting religious texts enables me to introduce the moral dimension within certain law, not only to move towards ethical animal representation on stage, but to highlight existing animal rights and welfare acts that morally account for nonhuman lives within several animal-based industries.

Animals are often portrayed as objects, rather than subjects, meaning nonhumans lack status; a focus that animal ethnography aims to shift. Vincent Leblan and Mélanie Roustan (2023) state that 'Ethical issues are central to

this line of enquiry, placing rights at the heart of the debate, and redistributing issues of responsibility, while still leaving its monopoly with humans' (p. 2). Therefore, as Chapter One introduces examples of animal representation, I stress that, despite anthropocentric attitudes that favour human perspectives, animals are morally relevant enough to be considered ethically in how humanity treats and represents them, specifically on stage in my case.

Chapter Two introduces speciesism, a key term in animal studies stemming from humanity's mistreatment of and discrimination against nonhumans. As a result of such prejudice, animals are subjected to their 'otherness', thus distinguishing them from humans as they lack rationality and consciousness, rendering them morally irrelevant in comparison. Considering animal 'otherness', Sune Borkfelt (2011) addresses 'Their otherness is somehow seen as something very basic, because we continue to think of it as a natural, rather than a cultural, phenomenon' (p. 137), where 'othering' an animal because of their species group has become a social norm.

Through introducing alterity and the notion of an animal 'other', I scrutinise such attitudes towards animals to lead into a posthuman framework that depicts ancestral connections between all living beings, thereby encouraging ethical animal representation. Furthermore, highlighting the unjust mistreatment animals face enables me to problematise the human-animal relationship, as I lead into Giorgio Agamben's depictions of life, *Zoe* and *bios*, to address how humanity additionally distinguishes itself from one another.

Moreover, I detail the speciesism debate within this chapter, engaging with key philosophers Peter Singer's anti-speciesist and Shelley Kagan's speciesist attitudes to uncover a general understanding of animal morality. Before I can understand how an animal can be ethically represented on stage, this chapter concludes by challenging the ethical implications within both interspecies performance and the positions within the speciesism debate to ensure the nonhuman is always acknowledged morally within both fields.

Chapter Three establishes 'ethics' as a philosophical framework that aims for good decision-making regarding animal engagement and representation. This chapter explores animal agency in an ethics of attentiveness, where I urge the

importance of viewing the animal morally as a co-performing agent that exceeds the nonhuman beyond a sign system, such as being perceived on stage as a prop or metaphor when placed alongside a human counterpart. I do so to lead into the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker, bringing in Critical Animal Studies and poetics in a performance context that challenges anthropocentrism³ to uncover how ethical animal representation can stem from acknowledging animal agency and the existing animal welfare acts that protect nonhuman lives.

Examined throughout this chapter is the notion that animals are present within Performance studies. I do so to later bring forward the ethics of attentiveness as a spectator, where the mid-1990s term “animal turn” sparked the acknowledgement of ‘animal consciousness’ in recent cultures (Budriesi, 2022, p. 8). Thereby, I encourage a rejection of speciesism as spectators can interrogate their relationship with animals and be deeply moved or affected by the presence of a ‘performing animal’ when considering animal representation on stage from a nonhuman perspective.

Finally, Chapter Four analyses O’Reilly’s interspecies work which looks at two examples of animal ethics in the context of performance. Firstly, O’Reilly’s creative practice is highlighted to showcase how she balances ethics, care and relation into her work before demonstrating these elements in the pieces I analyse: *Inthewrongplaceness* (2005) and *Falling Asleep with a Pig (FAWaP)* (2009). *Inthewrongplaceness* features O’Reilly naked on stage, embracing, cradling and intertwining her bare body with a pig cadaver. Audience members enter the performative space wearing latex gloves, replicating a laboratory setting where either body on stage can be moved and manipulated to highlight the exploitative nature of animal testing in a scientific setting. Contrastingly, *FAWaP* sees O’Reilly and live potbellied pig Deliah sharing a pig pen within an indoor and outdoor gallery exhibition. Here, audience members move freely around the space and observe both bodies in the gallery drift in and out of the shared universal habit of sleep. These specific examples enable me to explore the ethics of performance with a deceased and living nonhuman co-performer.

³ The favouring of the human perspective.

I have featured O'Reilly's interspecies work in this project because she is aware of how to replicate the status of a pig rather than its superior. O'Reilly highlights the ethical dimension within her work, stating:

It is very difficult for me to think of ethics as something that could create an ultimate reconciliation of well-being for all actors...So ethics must be something that is contingent, crucial and critical, but also specific to a time and place (Dervinytė, 2022, p. n.p).

Ultimately, O'Reilly offers practical insight into the key findings of my theoretical investigation regarding animal ethics in performance. She is a pioneer of interspecies performance as she has an awareness of the ethical implications human-animal co-performance can create; however, rather than this being a type of art to shun, she engages with animal poetics to pay attention to the existing welfare that cares for nonhuman lives to understand how these differ from her own, resulting in answering my focal question which is how can one ethically represent an animal as a co-performer.

Chapter One

A Historical Account of the Human-Animal Relationship: From Co-dependency to Oppression

As I aim to explore how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer, I first outline a broad timeline of the human-animal relationship, narrowing to the role of animals on stage. Moreover, I contextualise the coexistence of humans and animals from the Old Stone Age to the 21st century. I do so to demonstrate periods in history where, through domestication and industrialised exploitation, humans began representing animals as hunters, clothing, shelter, food, labourers and entertainers.

I trace animal representation within the human-animal relationship since the Paleolithic era to uncover the shift that introduced nonhumans to more exploitative environments, such as the entertainment industry. Through incorporating evidence of an obligation to morality in religious texts, I highlight a morality of relation between humans and nonhumans, suggesting that humanity has abandoned its moral responsibility to care for animals. I quote religious scripture to provide a written ethical framework, utilising this as a code of practice to morally consider human treatment and the representation of animals in both the entertainment and meat industries.

Furthermore, I emphasise that the 20th century saw the introduction of advocacy for animal rights and welfare acts to protect non-human lives in such industries. I feature animal welfare acts that account for animal agency and sentience not only in the entertainment industry but also in several animal food industries. This allows me to highlight the ethical concerns that such industries raise and feature existing welfare measures in place to protect nonhuman lives subjected to this exploitative treatment and representation.

Animals as Food

Since the Old Stone Age Paleolithic Period, human animals and nonhuman animals⁴ have co-existed and inhabited the Earth simultaneously, creating a two-million-year-old ancestral connection between humans and animals. Cary Wolfe (2011) encourages individuals to set aside the physical differences between a human and an animal to identify that ‘the human’ and ‘the animal’:

are relics of a philosophical humanism that flattens the actual complexity and multidimensionality of what are, in fact, many different ways of being in the world that are shared in myriad particular ways across species lines (p. 3).

Wolfe observes that humans and animals co-exist yet cannot fathom the other’s way of ‘being’ in the world, as this differs immensely from their own. There are shared universal habits amongst humans and animals, including eating, sleeping, breathing and co-creating; even so, humans and animals are distinct from one another’s species line and will therefore encounter these ways of being differently. Humans can only understand their way of existing, and trying to understand existence from an animal’s or another individual’s perspective can debase others’ legitimate experiences.

This deep-rooted connection between humans and animals dates back to the Paleolithic era, where they were of equal status at one point in time. The Old Stone Age was a period when humans and animals exhibited very similar behaviours and instincts, ultimately sharing one goal: survival (Zuk, 2013, p. n.p). To survive, animals hunted animals; likewise, humans hunted animals. Here, the life cycle of wild animals intersects with humanity’s need for survival, as animals are deprived of their freedom once they are dead and then represented as a source of food by humans. Both species needed to survive, but humanity’s physical capacity and ability to utilise stone tools or shaping tools when animals did not resulted in exploiting animals for survival.

Stone tools are known as ‘humanity’s first innovation’ (The Archaeologist, 2025, p. n.p), as humankind became equipped with the appropriate technology to improve their quality of life. Fundamentally, the Paleolithic era set the groundwork for

⁴ The term ‘human animal’ refers to a member of the human race. ‘Nonhuman animal’ applies when describing a nonhuman species, including animals and organisms.

human civilisation. Hammerstones, stone cores and stone flakes curated a collection of equipment for battering surfaces and the introduction of such tools not only curated weapons for survival advantages against predators, but additionally:

the cognitive demands of toolmaking likely drove the evolution of the human brain. The ability to plan, problem-solve, and transmit knowledge across generations laid the foundation for language, culture, and complex social structures (ibid.).

The development of stone tools aided humankind's social, labouring and environmental skills, thus benefiting their emotional and physical growth for centuries. Moreover, stone tools were later adapted into hunting tools such as an Acheulean (Warwick), a hand axe used to frighten or kill animals, and once Paleolithic early homo sapiens learnt that animals were a species to hunt and utilise as a food source, the skills they had adopted through the use of stone tools made it easier to target animals during hunts (The Historian, 2023, p. n.p).

As tools led to greater efficiency in hunting, there was a shift in viewing humans and animals as equally vulnerable. Stone tools provided humanity with mental and physical qualities that set them apart as apex hunters who viewed everything else as food, thus influencing their evolution and establishing their dominance. However, despite humans exerting their dominance as a species through possessing different hunting abilities from nonhumans, both species continued to share the survival habit of targeting animals throughout the Old Stone Age.

Animals as Clothing & Shelter

Transitioning into the Mesolithic period within the Middle Stone Age, hunting was a continued habit for human-animal survival. As nonhumans did not have the aid of shaping tools to carry out successful hunts, Bridgette Byrd O'Connor (no date) explains:

Most animals are social creatures. They come together in family groups or herds for protection, to raise their young, and to find food. Humans are similar to other animals in that they form groups, such as families or clans, to help the species survive (p. n.p).

The survival rate throughout the Mesolithic era was extremely low, leading humans and animals to instinctively form herds or small nomadic hunting groups for migrating across land. As evolving hunter-gatherers, humankind developed stone tools such as scrapers, hand axes, bows and arrows. The ongoing development of human technology made it easier to hunt megafauna, 'such as mastodons, sabre-toothed cats, giant ground sloths, woolly mammoths, giant bison, and deer' (Davidson, 2021, p. n.p), while animals relied on the physical advantages and strength of their herds.

Besides consumption during the Mesolithic era, humankind discovered other uses of nonhuman animals once their life cycle had ended. The relationship between humans and animals began to shift throughout the Mesolithic era, as, besides hunting for their meat, animal skin became desirable for clothing and shelter. The durability, sustainability and comfort of animal skins 'have long been valued particularly as raw materials for clothing (leather and wool), gloves (leather), shoes (leather), furniture (leather), blankets (wool), and other uses' (Scanes, 2018, p. 15).

As humankind continuously reproduced throughout the Stone Age, the demand for non-food uses of animals, such as their fibre for wool, fur or leather, grew very popular. Consequently, nonhumans supported and provided for humans, thus encouraging a dependency within their relationship. During the Mesolithic era, nonhuman animals became a representation of aid to humans, as they provided food, clothing or shelter. Ultimately, non-food uses for animals meant they became a species that catered to human needs, advancing human technology and civilisation.

Animals as Domesticates

Progressing into the New Stone Age Neolithic Period, human society advanced significantly as early homo sapiens 'could finally stay in one place because they cultivated their own food through agriculture and domesticating animals' (Novak, 2023, p. n.p). Throughout this era, humans transitioned from hunter-gatherers to farmers and began domesticating wildlife. Considering animal representation as food, clothing or shelter, the nonhuman's life cycle is specific to when it is killed and then used by humans. This is where animal exploitation takes place. Domestication, on the other hand, dictates the entire life cycle of nonhumans, as it was predicated upon the needs of humans to survive, thus strengthening humanity's dependency on nonhumans in the Neolithic Period.

Certain traits and characteristics influenced which mammalian species would be domesticated, as Scanes (2018) reveals:

Among the traits selected across animal species were docility, reproductive shifts, and decreased size (Larson et al., 2014). It is likely that, in addition, there was unintentional selection in capture or bias with slower and/ or younger animals more likely to be captured (p. 113).

Humans began domesticating smaller-framed animals with poorer agility, as they were more manageable; humans were selective about the animals they domesticated, often choosing those with advantageous traits that could support their evolving lifestyles. For example, dogs were domesticated from grey wolves to assist in hunting, where:

Those wolves less afraid of humans scavenged nomadic hunting camps and over time developed utility, initially as guards warning of approaching animals or other nomadic bands and soon thereafter as hunters, an attribute tuned by artificial selection (Driscoll, Macdonald and O'Brien, 2009, p. 89).

To highlight the dependency on animal domesticates, Richard Epstein (2005) explains, 'Because they use and value animals, owners will spend resources for their protection' (p. 149). As owners, it was the humans' responsibility to nurture their domesticated companions, ensuring they were supervised, well-fed and nourished to secure their safety and survival. Animals became valued by humans for their service, and domestication continued to develop when livestock, such as goats, sheep and cattle, were utilised to provide food sources, including milk, cheese and yoghurt (Scanes, 2018, p. 116).

The domestication of animals influenced how humanity operated throughout the Neolithic era when humans 'also developed new technologies, such as the wheel, which allowed for more efficient transportation and the development of new forms of labour' (Marcellus, 2023, p. n.p). The invention of the wheel advanced human technology as animals were domesticated and represented as labourers; cattle were not only used for food but also as a mode of transport, assistants in carrying cargo and farmhands.

Livestock assisted on farms by pulling on equipment and creating fertilisation from their faeces, whilst 'the Natufian hunter-gatherers developed tools such as the sickle and grinding stones to harvest and process wild grains' (Driscoll, Macdonald and O'Brien, 2009, p. 89), highlighting the growing dependency humans placed on nonhumans as resources to advance animal agriculture. Livestock and labouring assistance are examples of an animal's entire life cycle being tailored to the needs of humans, as ultimately:

With a reliable food source, human populations began to rise, technology for collecting grains further improved, and settlements initially encouraged by naturally abundant food led to larger settlements (ibid.).

Humans combining their hunting, farming, and agricultural efforts with nonhumans throughout the New Stone Age benefited humanity. Civilisation was established, and facilities, buildings, and communities expanded throughout the Neolithic era through collaboration in the human-animal relationship. The trust that humankind placed in the animal kingdom created a dependency that strengthened the human-animal relationship as nonhumans offered support and resources for the profit of the human species.

Furthermore, as humankind's mental abilities rapidly evolved, the balance within the human-animal relationship began to shift; humans were set apart from animals. Although both species have always shared similar universal habits, how human animals interacted with the Earth's resources, and how they represented animals throughout the Stone Age, introduced them to evolving emotional and physical abilities that asserted their dominance as a species, furthering the extent to which humans utilised and relied on nonhumans.

Animals as Entertainers

Through contextualising this historical timeframe, it is evident that human needs continuously expanded throughout the Stone Age. Each example of animal representation, such as food, clothing, shelter or domestication, is a result of humanity asking nonhumans for assistance over several centuries. Here, I provide such a broad overview of animal representation to narrow this history to animals being represented on stage as performers. As I aim to understand how an animal can be portrayed on stage ethically as a co-performer, I shall highlight initial appearances of animals in performance to comprehend primary examples of nonhuman representation on stage.

The extremities of animal exploitation and representation developed as humankind continued to utilise nonhumans as a resource for their needs. The public slaughtering of animals in first-century ancient Rome was deemed standard entertainment where spectators watched exotic animals fighting and slaughtering one another, or venatores, loaded warriors, in colosseums (Brinkhof, 2021, p. n.p). To add, Wilson (2015) explains:

Besides the mass execution of humans, the slaughter of wild animals, sometimes subjected to training before their death, was so extensive over so many centuries that wildlife populations across the empire were decimated (p. 5).

A wide array of animals were targeted in gladiatorial combats, indicating that a species that was once preyed on and killed for human survival was now actively selected to be publicly slaughtered for human entertainment. Unintentionally asserting themselves as entertainers, numerous breeds of animals were relied on for human spectacle, in addition to the existing needs humanity had exposed them to (ibid). Considering the Roman Empire as an example, introducing animals into the entertainment industry resulted in the entire life cycle of the animal supporting the human need for spectacle and being entertained.

Teresa Grant, Ignacio Ramos Gay and Claudia Alonso Recarte (2018) establish:

The Roman circuses certainly set the precedent for the exploitation of nonhuman others in the entertainment industry as we know it in contemporary culture, and in which the performing animal (be it in a circus, a theatre, a film, an aquarium, a zoo, a show, etc.) (p. 4).

The Roman and Greek Empires were the first instances where humanity placed a species of nature in an entertainment venue. Placing animals in a performative setting was another mode of harnessing human power over the life cycle of nonhumans, as:

More than the exhibition of the natural reality of the animal, the Roman games sought to capture it culturally (Boyde 2014), that is, to objectify it through forceful domination and through its projection within a theatricalized environment aimed at entertainment and symbolic of the superiority of man over the natural world (Shelton 2007) (ibid.).

Representing animals as entertainment, specifically across the Roman Empire, allowed humans to use performance as a mask to demonstrate their control over nonhumans, as the public slaughter of wild, ferocious animals implied that humans could dominate such “beasts” to entertain spectators.

Transitioning to AD 1500-1700, ‘Animal baiting, the pitting of dogs against other animals such as bulls and bears for public entertainment, was extremely popular in Early Modern England’ (Wright et al., 2025, p. 536). Moreover, the late 18th-century animal industry established zoos and circuses in the United Kingdom, expanding the entertainment industry. Animals were quickly represented as essential entertainers who humanity depended on for spectacle and financial gain once industries began generating public attention. Additionally, to transition to 1874, London Zoo started operating in the 19th century (Jacqueline Banerjee, no date, p. n.p).

London Zoo was opened to the general public, meaning ‘visitors could now stroll past the structures and enclosures’ (ibid.). During this period, the animals were not necessarily performing for human audiences; however, lions, tigers, elephants, and monkeys were kept in enclosed displays as entertainment for public spectators who freely wandered around each exhibition. Banerjee (no date) explains, ‘Caging and taming these imported animals undoubtedly reflected Britain's fascination with its vast overseas empire — and its feeling of superiority over it’ (ibid.), where the success of sourcing exotic wild animals and displaying them reinforced nonhumans as entertainers. Ultimately, nonhumans in entertainment established an industry in which humans asserted their dominance by profiting from animal exploitation.

The growing dependency on animals for financial gain solidified the success of travelling or settled circuses where exotic animals such as elephants, monkeys and “big” cats attracted audiences of all ages and classes (ibid.). Circus animals were required to perform tricks such as jumping through hoops or playing with a ball or prop, bringing joy to spectators fascinated by the animals' performative skills. When circuses were first introduced:

The concept of ‘cruelty’ was not recognised, with indifference towards, if not deliberate infliction of, suffering. And, as a source of inconvenience if not fear, wilderness or wild nature was still often disliked in the eighteenth century (Wilson, 2014, p. 23).

Primarily, taming and training wild animals for entertainment enabled humans to find power in their dislike for nonhumans and harness control over species they did not yet understand; ultimately, the exploitive nature of circuses was not an ethical concern until the mid-20th century.

In the 21st century, there is *now* a general understanding of cruelty in making nonhuman animals perform circus tricks for their human audience, ‘but they also should be there in the sense that they always have been, are part of the idea of circus. They are, after all, circus animals, and many of them may even have been born to it’ (Ridout, 2004, p. 58). In time, the animal's presence in the performance industry during the 18th to 19th centuries became an expectation, setting the precedent for exotic performing circus animals for years to come.

Animals as Moral Patients

After discussing the changing human-animal relationship and the evolution of human needs that nonhumans have supported for centuries, morality eventually comes into play regarding humanity's representation of animals. Morality refers to values and characteristics that distinguish right from wrong and good from bad. When comprehending a nonhuman's ability to act morally, Mark Rowland (2012) claims that 'They have interests that we are morally obliged to take into account when we make decisions that impact on them. They emerge, in other words, as moral patients (p.75). Animal morality examines whether nonhumans can surpass being recipients of treatment and decision-making as moral patients to become moral subjects capable of reason.

However, as animals lack self-consciousness and the rationality to distinguish good from bad, Steven Sapontzis' philosophical understanding of an animal's capability to act morally claims that only rational animals can be moral agents. Therefore, since animals are not human animals, they lack reason and cannot be moral agents (ibid., 78). Although animals are not moral agents in the sense that they cannot understand right from wrong, they remain moral patients who are worthy of good decision-making from humanity regarding their well-being.

Before the more specific focus on animal rights and welfare solidified in the 20th century, morality was prominent in religious texts that spanned across an array of time. I understand these texts are relevant to their time, place and context, which is why I am taking a specific approach when including such texts, rather than a universal one. With ethical animal representation comes moral consideration; therefore, I include religious texts objectively to introduce morality within scripture to navigate the position of animals in relation to humans.

According to religious texts in the Bible, the relationship between humans and animals 'is established from the very beginning of the biblical narrative and is woven throughout Scripture, highlighting the interconnectedness of all creation under God's sovereign design' (Bible Hub, no date, p. n.p). The dependency and companionship within the human-animal relationship are prominent throughout the scripture, reflecting both the dominion and stewardship roles assigned to humanity (ibid.).

Genesis 1:26-28 instructs that with their guardianship over animals, males and females must 'Be fruitful and multiply, and fill the earth and subdue it; rule over the fish of the sea and the birds of the air and every creature that crawls upon the earth.' (ibid.) In this instance, the notion of ruling is established, and does not entitle humanity to dictate over nonhuman lives; rather, there is a responsibility in place to advance the Earth whilst refraining from harming its resources.

I recall Genesis as an example of the positionality between humans and animals since the dawn of time, indicating there is a morality of relations between them. The Bible proposes an exceptionalist moral code that highlights beliefs deemed superior to Christians, for example. Not every individual will abide by such text; however, I include religious scripture as a moral compass of a close reading I carried out to navigate and interpret the implied understanding of a responsibility tailored towards humankind within the book of Genesis. Throughout the Bible, humans are blessed with an ethical responsibility to animals, often 'reflecting God's care and order in creation' (ibid.), where God placed an established rule and a code of conduct to ensure the safety and well-being of nonhumans. To follow this 'order', Proverbs 12:10 states, 'Whoever is righteous has regard for the life of his beast, but the mercy of the wicked is cruel' (OpenBible, no date, p. n.p).

Proverbs 12:10 reinforces that if animals are going to be used as a resource for humanity, then it is a privilege that should not be abused. The responsibility within this relationship appears one-sided as animals lack agency; however, I include this moral responsibility to stress that humans can therefore make decisions that benefit nonhumans, such as representing them ethically. If humanity abides by this moral responsibility and cares for nonhumans in such a way, 'this verse highlights the moral responsibility of humans to treat animals with kindness and care, reflecting a righteous character' (Bible Hub, no date, p. n.p).

If an animal is going to serve as a human resource, it must be respected, meaning 'In contrast to godly attitudes, a wicked person's approach to animals can't be anything more than cruelty. Even their "mercy," in such a case, is relatively harsh and abusive' (BibleRef, no date, p. n.p). If an individual is cruel yet presents themselves as kind, this questions their morality, as how one interacts with other humans can reflect their treatment of animals. Ultimately, God's guardianship placed

over humans was intended to highlight an individual's 'righteous character' above all else (Bible Hub, no date, p. n.p). Therefore, if one were to grant themselves power over animals and abuse the privilege of utilising animals as a human resource, this would be an injustice that does not align with God's code of conduct to care for nonhuman lives.

The position of the animal in relation to morality within religious texts is also prominent in other religions, such as Buddhism. For example, 'Buddhism is known to be a religion that practices and promotes peace for both human and non-human animals' (Kihlander, 2019, p. n.p). At some point in history, humanity thought that animals were placed on Earth as a resource for them rather than as a species co-existing with them. To objectively look at another example of religious text that indicates a morality of relation where no individual should subject nonhumans to unjust suffering, the Buddha in the Dhammapada stated, 'All beings tremble before danger. All fear death. When you consider this, you will not kill or cause someone else to kill. All beings fear before danger. Life is dear to all' (ibid.).

Through highlighting evidence of morality in scripture and considering earlier examples of animal representation in society, it is evident that the tacit moral responsibility placed on humankind as agents to guard animals has been slowly abandoned. This shift perhaps happened during the Neolithic era, which is also known as the Anthropocene, an epoch where humanity became the most influential species as its inhabitancy on Earth has had 'a lasting - and potentially irreversible - influence on its systems, environment, processes and biodiversity'⁵ (Pavid, no date, p. n.p). Tracing how human needs, which nonhumans support, have expanded throughout the centuries, humankind has transformed animals from subjects into objects that represent a resource.

I introduce morality in select examples of religious texts to understand ethics. Over time, utilising animals, which are identified in scripture as subjects, resulted in humanity disregarding their moral responsibility to protect animals by dismissing the codes of care present throughout religious texts. Instead, the rise of the Anthropocene made it easier for humans to control not only the current climate but

⁵ Biodiversity refers to the different kinds of life that contribute to the Earth's ecosystem such as plants, nonhuman animals and nonhuman organisms.

also the lives of nonhumans. Here, exploitation then occurs through the representation of animals as objects that contributed to humanitarian social, political and cultural advances.

Animal Advocacy: Rights & Welfare

I highlighted a morality of relations between humans and animals that is prominent within religious texts in the previous section to introduce law, specifically the legal precautions in place to protect the well-being of animals from the 20th century. Religious scripture within the Bible depicts an example of a moral code for individuals to follow regarding their treatment of animals; however, the establishment of animal rights activism in the early 20th century set the precedent for welfare acts that must be adhered to. Animal representation on stage and the treatment of nonhuman performers were not morally questioned until the early 20th century. Moral implications associated with animal representation ultimately raise ethical concerns for nonhumans; however, this concern is raised when rights and welfare acts that protect animal lives are ignored.

I detail 'ethics' in Chapter Three more thoroughly; however, ethics sets the precedent for good decision-making in one's choices, establishing a high moral standard that questions what is morally good or bad for the world around them (Cambridge University, no date, p. n.p). Certain examples of law showcase a moral dimension, specifically when comprehending animal rights and welfare, which is a result of morally considering nonhuman lives. Identifying regulations in place provides an understanding of the ethics of human-animal collaboration when positioning an animal on stage.

The Performing Animals Regulation (Act) was established in 1925, which 'requires any person who exhibits or trains any performing (vertebrate) animal to be registered with a local authority' (Animal Legal and Historical Centre, 2018, p. n.p). Animals in performance became an art that one had to be authorised to carry out. Not everyone had the creative control to work or collaborate with 'performing animals'. Therefore, the 20th century shifted the human-animal relationship as scientific advancements and animal rights movements put the United States and Britain's treatment of nonhumans under scrutiny (The Woof, no date, p. n.p).

In 1975, philosopher Peter Singer drove the animal rights movement with his work in his essay *Animal Liberation*, where Singer:

argued that animals deserved equal consideration of their interests, especially their capacity to suffer, influencing a new generation of animal welfare advocates and prompting discussions around vegetarianism and veganism (ibid.).

Singer's understanding of an animal's ability to suffer moves nonhumans beyond representation as objects or resources. Moreover, animals were gradually contemplated morally as subjects with emotional intelligence and the ability to feel. Considering human needs that objectify animals, such as entertainers and domestic animals, public discourse around the ethical treatment and representations of nonhumans in these fields stemmed from Singer's work on the modern-day animal rights movement.

Here, a foundation was laid regarding 'contemporary discussions about animal law, advocating for policies that reflect a deeper understanding of animal sentience and the importance of legal protections' (Law & More, 2025, p. n.p). Stemming from Singer's influential work in 1975, the 1970s saw a split between animal welfare and animal rights. To clarify the difference between the two, animal rights consider that animals matter morally, like humans. Therefore, legislation was introduced to protect animal lives from unnecessary pain or suffering. Animal welfare, specifically, is guided by a moral compass that ensures nonhumans are cared for as agents and treated in a way that benefits them (Animal Welfare Council, no date, p. n.p).

In the context of contemporary theatre, Singer's notion of animal suffering influenced how nonhumans were represented and treated in the entertainment industry from the mid-20th century onwards. Without first introducing the concept of animal rights and welfare regulations that protect the well-being of animals, it is not easy to then understand how an animal can be ethically represented on stage, specifically in contemporary interspecies performance.

Considering how animals can be represented in both the natural and theatrical world, Gina Darwin-Gitonga (2022) reveals:

The limbo that animals present between the fictional and natural worlds offers an opportunity for reflection and is one that post-modernists take advantage of as they seek to deconstruct and destroy the anthropocentric attitudes between them (p. n.p).

If theatre acts as a mirror of society, economic, social and ethical concerns can be acknowledged when presented in a theatrical space, encouraging reflection on these issues. The animal may not have the capacity to 'act' out a role; however, placing a

nonhuman, a species that a posthuman framework suggests homo sapiens have ancestral connections to, on stage, enables the animal to perform. From here, the nonhuman can perform societal issues that reflect the unjust representation of nonhumans in certain industries.

When animal legislation is adhered to by the theatre-maker placing the animal on stage, the human and animal not only ethically co-perform, but performance becomes a valuable tool to scrutinise other animal industries. These include the meat, dairy and poultry industries. Similar to animal rights and welfare acts that protect animals in performance, there is legislation that aims to protect the well-being of animals in the food industry.

Factory farming, specifically, is often composed of multinational corporations that exploit nonhuman lives to produce meat, dairy and eggs. Similar to domestication, factory farming dictates the entirety of nonhuman lives to assist human food needs. The Human League (2020) reveals that 'From physical and emotional abuse to the absolute denial of freedom and the ability to conduct natural behaviours, animals on factory farms endure horrific, frightening, and unnaturally shortened lives' (p. n.p). Factory farming ignores any sense of morality, subjecting 130 billion animals globally, including cows, pigs, chickens and fish, to inhumane conditions where the animals are confined together, deprived of sunlight, and subjected to genetic mutations (ibid.).

Industries such as factory farming represent nonhumans as products for human consumption, erasing any moral responsibility to care for nonhuman lives. As a cry to end the suffering of animal livestock, the UK's Farm Animal Welfare Council established 'The Five Freedoms' (1979); these include:

1. Freedom from thirst, hunger, and malnutrition
2. Freedom from discomfort and exposure
3. Freedom from pain, injury, and disease
4. Freedom from fear and distress
5. Freedom to express normal behaviour (The Human League, 2020, p. n.p).

The Five Freedoms were introduced a few years after Singer influenced the animal rights movement, accounting for the physical and mental needs of nonhumans. The Five Freedoms were framed to this morality of relation between humans and

animals, as 'The inclusion of psychological needs was a significant step forward in acknowledging animal sentience' (RSPCA, no date, p. n.p).

In a performance context, animal welfare acts that are tailored to animal sentience in entertainment curate regulations that ethically consider the nonhuman, where Cruelty Farm (no date) reveals:

They provide a framework for defining acceptable practices, setting standards for care, and establishing guidelines for the treatment of animals. Effective regulation can help mitigate potential abuses and ensure that animals are treated with respect and dignity (p. n.p).

Setting the premise for how animals should be ethically represented and incorporated into interspecies performance with Singer's notion in mind, Bill Berloni and his animal work, specifically with dogs on Broadway beginning in 1975, 'is renowned for revolutionising the humane and ethical use of rescue animals in entertainment' (Theatrical Animals, no date, p. n.p). Berloni's influential work in television, film and theatre is one example of how humans and nonhumans could collaborate humanely as co-performers on stage.

To illustrate, Berloni utilised toys and treats to interact with and care for the animals in the performative space, setting aside human dominance and abuse to establish positive reinforcement where the animal chooses to do something willingly in the performance space (Animal Fair, no date, p. n.p). Specifically in a performance context, adhering to existing animal legislation is essential to comprehend how humans and animals can ethically co-perform, as these regulations consider animals morally.

Overall, I have contextualised the broad history of the human-animal relationship to highlight the development of animal portrayal, specifically representation throughout the years. Contextualising how the human-animal relationship has shifted provides an understanding of humanity's abandonment of its implied moral responsibility to supervise animals, challenging how humans can view nonhumans morally, as this is essential when comprehending ethical animal representation. To highlight animal morality, I included a brief overview of animal welfare regulations that protect animals in several industries, as animals on stage creates a space to address the nature of such incorporations. In Chapter Two, I will now introduce speciesism and animal 'otherness' to further understand how humans

view not only animals morally, but also themselves, in an attempt to achieve ethical animal representation on stage through blurring the human-animal distinction.

Chapter Two

Speciesism & Animal 'Otherness': Problematizing the Human-Animal Relationship

After contextualising the human-animal relationship and the development of nonhuman representation over several centuries, the following section introduces a key term in animal studies discourse: speciesism. Within speciesism, animal exploitation by humankind is justified due to its superiority. I have highlighted the dependency placed on nonhumans to support humanity's needs, to inspect the status shift within the human-animal relationship. I now propose that speciesism is the root cause of animals experiencing differing treatment and exploitation in how they are portrayed or represented socially or culturally, such as entertainers or food.

As a result of the discrimination animals face because they are not deemed human, animals are subjected to their 'otherness' despite being moral patients. I introduce 'otherness' to highlight the human-animal distinction that strips the bond of responsibility within this relationship. Additionally, I challenge the notion of 'othering' to scrutinise the unjust treatment animals endure, as I introduce Giorgio Agamben's *Zoe* and *bios* to indicate that humanity also distinguishes itself from one another.

I then detail speciesism as part of a wider context, introducing a posthuman framework that highlights an ancestral connection between humans and animals. I do so to question human hierarchy, emphasising throughout the chapter that despite their lack of agency, animals possess moral worth as moral patients. From here, the speciesism debate is introduced to highlight Peter Singer's anti-speciesist argument and Shelley Kagan's speciesist view, highlighting the differing attitudes taken when considering nonhuman animals morally.

The two positions in the speciesism debate are then problematised to ensure that the nonhuman is always the focal concern within this, as animal erasure results in ethical abandonment of the nonhuman's moral worth. Moreover, I also challenge interspecies performance to highlight the exploitive nature of this art form so as not to dismiss the ethical implications associated with this type of performance, before later understanding how the animal can be represented ethically in this space.

Defining Speciesism & 'Otherness'

Animal rights activist Richard Ryder introduced the 1970 term 'speciesism' to highlight the absence of moral consideration for nonhumans and a lack of acknowledgement of animal ethics. Ryder first introduced speciesism as a term branching from attitudes and behaviour harboured within 'isms' such as racism, sexism and classism, where there is then an ethical dimension. Australian philosopher Peter Singer expanded on Ryder's definition of speciesism in 1975, where:

Singer took up Ryder's term, but focused his definition on the broadly epistemic basis of discriminatory behavior: he characterized speciesism as "a prejudice or attitude of bias in favor of the interests of members of one's own species and against those of members of other species" (Singer 2009 [1975], 6, emphasis added) (Albersmeier, 2021, p. 513).

Speciesism was coined from anthropocentrism, where humankind prioritises the interests of itself over animals, purely because they are not human. I introduce speciesism as this not only erases the implied bond of moral responsibility humans have to animals, but it is also demonstrated later as an attitude Kira O'Reilly adopts to reject speciesism within her interspecies work through eliminating the notion of status between herself and a pig.

In a performance context, speciesism corrupts ethical animal representation on stage as Borkfelt (2011) explains, 'We simply tend to place non-human animals in an entirely different category from our human others'⁶ (p. 138). Speciesism is the result of humans distinguishing themselves from animals, ultimately creating a difference in treatment towards nonhumans because of their 'otherness'. As an 'other':

Non-human animals are arguably placed in a constant, almost irredeemable state of alterity and are unable to speak for themselves from this othered position, which distinguishes their otherness from that of humans (ibid., 137).

The notion of animal 'alterity', the idea that a species is categorised as an 'other', deems the lives of nonhumans as inferior to those of the human species, thus diminishing their perspective. Considering this prejudice, speciesism becomes a

⁶ 'We' refers to humankind in this quotation.

descriptive term that is important in highlighting the notion of a human displaying isolation and discrimination towards any species that is not regarded as anthropoid⁷.

If speciesism were to be used instead as a normative concept, such as racism or sexism, individuals could be encouraged to embrace animal morality regarding nonhumans as subjects with the same social standing as they would account for their fellow humans, viewing the animal not necessarily as an 'other'. Animals may not be able to differentiate right from wrong; however, humans can. Therefore, it is morally right to treat animals ethically, and Bill Berloni's interspecies work, detailed under 'Animal Advocacy: Rights and Welfare' in Chapter One, highlights an example of how care and ethics can combine to remove human dominance in interspecies performance.

Fundamentally, I note animal 'otherness' to highlight that, despite being an 'other', disregarding animal alterity risks eliminating consideration of animal morality. Richie Nimmo (2016) suggests:

the erasure of alterity is intricately bound up with the imposition of relations of control, domination or dependency...the well-intentioned anthropomorphic impulse to bring animals near risks an unwitting enactment of the modernist tendency to treat the world as 'raw material for humanization' (Haraway 1991, 198) (p. 32).

Ultimately, comprehending that animals experience either harmful or careful treatment is vital to consider when assigning any ethical value to the term speciesism. Animal morality can be challenged within speciesism and could explore mapping nonhumans onto a human domain as subjects, similarly to us; however, this must be carried out in a way that benefits the animal, such as considering how this 'other' could be represented on stage as a subject, specifically a co-performer.

⁷ Anthropoid is used here to describe classifying a human being.

Why Engage with Speciesism?

To understand how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer, engaging with speciesism enables an understanding of what the term entails and the different attitudes individuals adopt when considering an animal's moral standing. I cannot explore the approaches theatre-makers, specifically Kira O'Reilly, take to ethically represent animals on stage without first highlighting the implications associated with individuals morally considering animals in general.

To elaborate, speciesism enables me to question the bond of moral responsibility in the human-animal relationship. Considering a morality of relation between humans and nonhumans, one individual may be a speciesist who views animals as an inferior species group, resulting in said individual mistreating and discriminating against animals. Another individual may be an anti-speciesist who believes equal treatment should be handed to all species, human or animal.

Despite one's attitude, animals are at the forefront of speciesism. An ethical dimension is suggested here, where:

SPECIESISM is customarily defined as “difference in treatment based on an appeal to species membership” (Graft 1997, 107), the belief “that membership in a particular species is morally relevant” (Bernstein 2004,380),and “the belief that, as a matter of fact, the division between humans and other animals is morally significant” (Holland 1984, 291) (Albersmeier, 2021, p. 513.).

Speciesism highlights the notion of human prejudice where humanity holds itself in a higher regard than animals. However, speciesism can highlight the bond of responsibility between humans and animals, as through being born on Earth, existing as a physical body and habituating the world as an entity, everyone and everything is morally significant regardless of species. Ultimately, speciesism enables me to highlight the moral value nonhuman animals possess as moral patients, which is vital when exploring examples of ethical animal representation on stage.

Problematizing 'Othering'

Perhaps what distinguishes an animal from a human is that this 'other' is not a moral subject in the sense that it cannot distinguish right from wrong or possess the capacity to act upon these principles accordingly, like a human. Even so, despite all being moral subjects, humans have not only caused a divide between animals but also amongst themselves. Reintroducing the notion of 'otherness', Borkfelt (2011) explains that the way animals are represented influences how humans perceive nonhumans and ultimately, their treatment towards them, revealing:

They can also influence our perceptions, and thus ultimately our othering, of some human groups, which we may somehow associate with those non-human animals or with the places where these animals live (p. 139).

Considering how animals are discriminated against for their 'otherness' in species, humankind has created divides between themselves depending on class, sex, religion and race. Therefore, I suggest that segregating a nonhuman for their 'otherness' creates an unnecessary distinction between humans and animals, as 'othering' evokes questioning humanity's treatment of one another to understand the reasoning for a difference in treatment towards animals.

To comprehend human life, Philosopher Giorgio Agamben and his work on control and power have affected this understanding. Drawing influence from Aristotle, a 'continual source of reflection by Agamben' is *Zoe* and *bios*, two terms that Agamben identifies as 'descriptors of life' (Mambrol, 2018, p. n.p). Agamben's term '*Zoe*— refers to life as bare physical survival, including biological reproduction and domestic labour' (ibid.). *Zoe* refers to an individual confined to "bare life", or in other words, 'at the animal level of necessity, rather than to achieve a fulfilling way of life as *bios*' (ibid). Essentially, *Zoe* applies to everything that lives and exists before dying; it is simply a state of being in the world with little power.

On the other hand, '*bios* is the sphere of politics proper – of the polis – the sphere of freedom and the creation of a form of life' (ibid), where there is a notion of existing freely and openly as a fully realised human being with human rights. Here, Agamben identifies power dynamics and elements of status in humankind. Individuals identified as *Zoe* experience this idea of "bare life", which is existence at its most basic, essential form. *Bios* hold power and superiority and are therefore in a

position where they can dispense of *Zoes* in whatever way deemed appropriate, as they are inferior and expendable (Raja, 2022, 02:45-03:10).

The life of *bios* is a level of freedom that Agamben discloses that slaves, women and children, despite having human rights, cannot rise to. Therefore, a division and an 'othering' can be created between *Zoe* and *bios*, a human and another human, just as easily as a divide between humans and animals. Considering morality, a notion of hierarchy from *bios* results in abandoning ethical consideration for *Zoe*, thus eliminating this bond of responsibility between all living beings indicated within scripture.

An example where humans dismiss their moral responsibility and fail to acknowledge the rights of those in their own species is the Taliban and their treatment of women. Raja (2022) identifies that although:

in the chronic explanation of rights, women are qualified life. They have rights, they have privileges. In the politics unleashed by the Taliban, women are reduced to the level of *Zoe* as passive right holders, not as active right holders (ibid., 03:20-03:40).

Despite being fully qualified physical beings, women can be subjected to discrimination and erased of moral worth due to their gender. In this case, women are identified as *Zoe*, passive rights holders. This means they cannot make a change as they are not in control of their own lives. In this example, a *bios* is a man. As a man, in this respect, you are considered an active rights holder, as you are in a position of power to make a difference and take action. Although every human is a physically qualified being, identifying someone as a passive rights holder (*Zoe*) or an active rights holder (*bios*) is another way to understand one's identity in the world. This exceeds considering an individual as a *Zoe* or *bios* due to one's race, ethnicity, sexuality, gender, or class.

It is, however, vital to make note of race, ethnicity, sexuality, gender or class as they are determining factors in discriminatory beliefs within racism, sexism and classism. Through identifying these terms, divides within the human-human relationship are highlighted, and Mohammed Sofiane Mesbahi (2014) reveals that 'it is the dominant isms throughout human history that have caused the upmost damage and division within our societies' (p. n.p). These isms, such as racism and sexism, are formed out of ignorance, fear, and prejudice, not only resulting in discrimination as a result of 'othering', but they are harmful within the human-human

relationship, often resulting in personal disagreements and fallouts or larger, wide-scale conflicts and wars.

Considering human life, isms create space for personal, social and political issues to present themselves within the human-human relationship. Sofiane Mesbahi (2014) suggests that:

Psychologically, it is an act of violence towards the Self to define ourselves as a communist or socialist, a leftist or liberation, an anarchist or neoconservative, or even as Christian, Jew, Hindhu, Buddhist, Theosophist and so on (p. n.p).

No matter how one identifies themselves sexually, religiously or culturally, there will always be a divide and the notion of 'otherness'. 'Othering' can therefore appear inevitable; however, the status of humans as *Zoe* or *bios* is dependent on context, such as not every woman is controlled by the Taliban, for example. Changeability presents itself here alongside the opportunity to reconsider the position of not only human life, but also nonhuman life, depending on the determining factors of one's moral standing regarding their context.

Despite the changeability of one's position, divisions amongst humankind will always arise, and one's religion, culture, race, sexuality, age, or class will be deemed morally significant. A difference in treatment or division within the human-human relationship is always identified and labelled as an ism, a disagreement or even a wide-scale conflict. Understanding *Zoe* and *bios*, as well as passive and active rights holders or isms within the human-human relationship, helps showcase that humans can discriminate against their species as easily as they can against nonhuman animals. This suggests that:

an increasing number of philosophers have argued that while humans are different in a variety of ways from each other and other animals, these differences do not provide a philosophical defense for denying non-human animals moral consideration (Gruen and Monsó, 2024, p. n.p).

I detail human life to highlight that no species, human or nonhuman, is exempt from discrimination. Considering ethical animal representation, specifically on stage, the bond of moral responsibility between each living being must be recalled to signify that each species is morally relevant and should be accounted for ethically. If divides, isms and implications within the human-human relationship are morally substantial to the extent they are named and addressed, then said distinctions within the human-animal relationship should hold equal moral significance.

Speciesism as Part of a Wider Context

Suppose human animals and nonhuman animals all possess moral worth but are prone to discrimination; yet it is solely nonhumans who are continuously subjected to unjust representation. In that case, one could ask, 'Is there something distinctive about humanity that justifies the idea that humans have moral status while non-humans do not?' (ibid.). After highlighting the progression of humankind's mental and physical advancements throughout the Stone Age, humans were established as the dominant species due to their moral agency. This could be the so-called "distinction" that sets humans apart from animals, as humans are self-aware individuals who make their own decisions or choices when nonhumans cannot do so.

Dismissing the notion that *bios control Zoe*, all humans are placed on Earth with the implied understanding that they are moral agents bonded to each living thing by responsibility, as they are capable of thinking and acting. Unfortunately, the nonhuman lacks agency and does not have the physical ability to vocalise its suffering; however, reiterating Rowland's findings in Chapter One, Grace Clement (2013) suggests:

Animals may be the recipients of moral (or immoral) treatment, or be moral patients, but only humans are truly moral agents. However, animals can act for moral reasons on the basis of moral emotions (p. 1).

An animal harbouring moral emotions means they are capable of experiencing feelings of fear, anger and pain, for example. Perhaps what dismisses humans of unjust representation and thus subjects nonhumans to such is that humanity understands that it possesses the agency to expose others to moral wrongdoings; it is, however, only nonhumans that cannot comprehend ethically questionable treatment and instead receive it. Regardless of their lack of consciousness, the very fact that animals experience moral emotions highlights the importance of morality. The ability to experience moral emotions outweighs one's agency, thus urging the importance of the bond of responsibility to animals when ethically considering and representing them.

As nonhumans are not moral agents, this could be the distinction that hands human animals superiority and thus entitles them to a higher moral status. Ultimately, this distinction reverts to speciesism, where human animals are favoured and prioritised over nonhuman animals. However, there is now an understanding that

any species can be subjected to discrimination or mistreatment regardless of their moral status. If each species, entity or physical being has moral status, then humans and animals alike morally matter. Here, speciesism is part of a broader context which emphasises the moral responsibility humans have to animals.

I set out the moral status of animals in such detail to indicate that, although they lack agency, this does not excuse unfair representation and unethical treatment. Instead, understanding that humans and animals matter morally suggests blurring the line of distinction between humans and animals to reject status, aiming for equal representation of nonhumans. To eliminate the idea of status between humans and animals, posthumanism is a framework that interrogates the human species as a category. Posthumanism challenges human hierarchy to find connections between humans and other entities (Rogers and Hamilton-McKenna, 2023, p. n.p). Ivan Callus (2022) elaborates, stating that:

The posthuman assemblage therefore dismantles a worldview in which the human is the ideal and centre of life. It is an assemblage whose identity is informed by its shared evolutionary history with other animals, its continued reliance on and relationship with other sentient and non-sentient entities, and its future co-evolution with modern technologies (p. 171).

Posthumanism challenges anthropocentrism, suggesting that if humans, animals, organisms, and entities all exist simultaneously, status amongst species lines is eliminated through this ancestral connection.

Throughout this chapter, speciesism is introduced to showcase anti-speciesist attitudes adopted by individuals when considering animal morality. This mistreatment is identified to encourage this posthuman framework that challenges individuals to view everyone and everything with equal moral status as equal subjects, as 'embracing posthumanism could heal the perceived gap between the human and non-human' (Oberauer , 2021, p. n.p). Here, the distinction between humans and animals can be blurred to reject speciesism and achieve ethical representation or treatment regardless of one's species.

Discussing the Positions

Similar to how complications arise in speciesism, where humans attempt to consider nonhumans as moral subjects, embracing posthumanism is also difficult. There is an understanding that no species or being is spared from discrimination, and instead, every living thing stems from the same matter. However, humans cannot refrain from mistreating one another; therefore, some may dismiss the ancestral connections that posthumanism proposes, as well as find it difficult to consider animal morality.

As I explore how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer, I now set out the speciesism debate to highlight the importance of acknowledging the moral worth of nonhumans. The speciesism debate places animal ethics at the forefront of discussing how humans treat animals, engage with them, view them and represent them to refrain from possessing an anthropocentric⁸ perspective.

To begin, Peter Singer's side of the speciesism debate prioritises viewing humans and nonhumans as moral subjects of equal moral worth, thus ensuring the human perspective is not prioritised. Rooted in his influential mid-20th-century animal rights findings, François Jacquet (2022) reveals Singer's arguments in his two books *Animal Liberation* (1975) and *Practical Ethics* (1979), where Singer proposes:

- (1) We should give equal consideration to like interests.
- (2) If we should give equal consideration to like interests, then we should give equal consideration to the equal interests of humans and non-humans.
- (3) Therefore, we should give equal consideration to the equal interests of humans and non-humans (p. 397).

Singer's notion of 'equal consideration to like interests', as highlighted in Chapter One, moves nonhumans beyond representation as objects because they are acknowledged as moral subjects, worthy of equal ethical consideration to a human counterpart. Singer's position within the speciesism debates relates to ideas present in posthumanism that suggest erasing moral status amongst species lines. Oberauer (2022) urges:

if we want to heal our relationship with the natural world, we have to let go of the idea that we are 'different' or 'special.' The posthuman decentralisation of the human

⁸ Anthropocentric is used to describe a view that holds humankind with more importance than animals.

requires us to release our sense of self-importance and embrace the interconnectivity and interdependence of everything (p. n.p).

By considering humans and animals equally, Singer strips humans of their presumed superiority and instead hands all species similar moral status. Singer's notion and beliefs are rooted in posthumanism, introducing a moral compass where, through abiding by the tacit bond of responsibility, one is entitled to equality by existing and being in the world, regardless of species.

Sitting on the opposing side of the speciesism debate is philosophy professor Shelley Kagan, who harbours a more speciesist perspective. Kagan critiques Singer's side of the argument and notes that equal interest should not amount to equal consideration, as he introduces a counterexample that declares:

Intuitively, the interests of bad people matter less than the equal interests of good people. In other words, deserved suffering counts for less than undeserved suffering...If equal interests should receive unequal weight depending on whether their bearers are innocent or guilty, then not all equal interests should receive equal weight (Jacquet, 2022, p. 389).

Kagan's side of the speciesism debate lacks an ethical dimension, as he dismisses the interests of animals and focuses solely on those of people. Kagan proposes that with humans, equal interests are often determined by one's context and behaviour. If equal interest is determined by one's behaviour and actions as a being in the world, then consideration for humans should be granted based on their moral similarities, thus separating the "good" from the "bad". Animals are then eliminated from Kagan's side of the debate as nonhumans lack the agency to determine moral behaviours.

Moreover, I introduce the speciesism debate to highlight the difficulty faced when considering animal morality, something that must be acknowledged if the ethical representation of an animal on stage is to be achieved. Critical Animal Studies (CAS) has argued 'that rather than conceptually romanticising our relationships with other beings and theorising the beauty of our shared encounters, we should focus on real animals and their actual life situations' (Westerlaken, 2018, p. n.p). Ultimately, uncovering how the animal can be carefully introduced in the context of performance is important; however, it is more important to understand *how* this can be achieved by acknowledging that there are still distinct differences in circumstances between humans and animals, resulting in different treatment, which Kagan highlights in his argument.

Problematizing Interspecies Performance & the Positions

Considering the conflicting sides of the speciesism debate, the animal is always situated within the ethical forefront. The fact that the nonhuman is accounted for and incorporated into the speciesism debate suggests that there is a consensus among humans that animals, despite their 'otherness', are morally relevant enough to be accounted for when placed against their human counterparts. However, although Singer and Kagan present strong arguments in the speciesism debate, they leave room for criticism.

Both Singer and Kagan are humans. As the dominant species that possesses moral agency, they have the power to give a voice to animals and advocate for their rights. Animals do not possess the moral agency or physical ability to speak for themselves; ultimately, humans are bonded by their responsibility to animals, such as giving them a voice, even if this means exploiting them. Arguably, a form of animal exploitation is interspecies performance. It cannot be denied that interspecies performance is a powerful tool that allows a human animal to share the creative space with a nonhuman animal. However, I utilise the following section to problematise interspecies performance, the very art form that introduces animals to the stage and thus, representation in such a setting.

Before I analyse O'Reilly's interspecies work as a representative example of how she highlights animal ethics to portray and represent a nonhuman as a co-performer alongside herself on stage, I want to draw attention to the ethical implications within this type of performance, so as not to dismiss these. When I refer to 'interspecies performance', I focus 'primarily on performance made in arts contexts and less so on the popular performance practices involving animals such as circus, the performativity of phenomena like big-game hunting' (Cull Ó Maoilearca and Fitzgerald-Allsopp, 2014, p. 9). I detailed the early appearances of animals in circuses, for example, to highlight the first instances of animals in a performance setting. I use this as a means to narrow this broad frame of early animal representation in performance, featured in Chapter One, to focus specifically on that in contemporary interspecies performance.

I am not dismissing that understanding how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer is not morally

questionable. The very act of placing an animal on stage raises ethical concerns as 'Interspecies performance can present fundamental challenges- but also creative opportunities- to presumptions of agency according to its traditional humanist associations with the exertion of subjective mastery and control' (ibid., 12). The stage may be an unnatural setting for an animal, yet engaging with nonhumans through interspecies performance enables theatre-makers to explore the nonhumans' negotiation of 'consent, refusal, resistance and choice' (ibid.). Through doing so, the animal is elevated to the status of co-performer, acting as an agent who can make creative choices in the performative space.

Before any animal can be ethically represented on stage as a co-performer, the animal must first be subjected to this setting. Although select theatre-makers feature nonhumans in their interspecies work to scrutinise animal representation in the meat, cosmetic or science industries, other artists may engage with animals to benefit their work, eliminating the morality of relations between humans and animals. Additionally, interspecies performance may introduce the opportunity for humans and animals to collaborate creatively; however, nonhuman performers cannot be compensated for their performative work the same way a human can due to their lack of agency.

Despite their lack of agency, nonhumans remain the focal point of ethical concern within interspecies performance and speciesism. I now reintroduce Springer and Kagan's arguments within the speciesism debate to frame this as part of a performance context to a morality of relations between humans and animals, challenging interspecies performance-making to ensure the nonhuman is treated as a moral subject.

In response to Kagan's opinion within the speciesism debate, Singer introduced the view that '(4) All humans are equal' (Jacquet, 2022, p. 400), highlighting a notion that is not only a social normality, but a moral one. Although Singer's intentions behind this claim may seem pure, as it reiterates this idea of equal interests receiving equal consideration, it could be misinterpreted 'either as an empirical description—all humans have the same capacities—or as a moral norm—all humans count equally' (ibid., 401).

Singer presents a complicated case, identifying that if 'all humans are equal' entails that all humans undergo shared circumstances and experiences, or if it is the basic fact that they are of the same species line and therefore all moral agents. Essentially, circumstance (experience) against reality (being) makes it difficult to identify equal consideration as these differ for every human subject. Additionally, Singer's argument unintentionally erases the nonhuman from his argument as he focuses on human subjects and disregards the moral standing of nonhumans.

However, performance gains something from speciesism here, as ethical concerns for nonhuman performers are often eliminated in interspecies performance due to the human performer's moral agency. Therefore, it should be emphasised 'if all humans are equal, this is in the sense that we should give equal weight to the equal interests of all subjects, *human or not*' (ibid.). Ultimately, Singer's argument emphasises that animals may lack agency but not moral worth; however, in a performance context, this does not necessarily entail that nonhumans should participate in performance in the same way as humans, as issues of refusal and consent cannot be discussed. Within Singer's argument, it is much too complicated to say all humans are equal and that equal consideration should be given to like interests, as it has been revealed that this leaves room for interpretation and raises questions about who or what this applies to.

Moreover, Kagan's argument can also be critiqued. Kagan erases the ethical dimension within the speciesism debate and introduces an 'othering' that distinguishes humans and animals, opposing a posthuman framework. Jacquet reveals:

Ultimately, however, Kagan supports a view he calls "modal personism": we should grant special consideration to the interests of modal persons—that is, subjects who either are or could have been rational and self-conscious (ibid., 395).

Opposed to Singer and his notion of granting equal consideration to equal interests (humans and nonhumans), Kagan defends speciesism by believing that more consideration should be given to humans. Kagan prioritises the perspective of humans as they do not lack consciousness and are capable of decision-making, arguing that if humans have the power to make decisions for themselves and others, they also permit themselves to make decisions for animals.

Kagan's side of the debate harbours a speciesist point of view that diminishes the implied bond of responsibility to care for nonhumans by disregarding that they are recipients of any moral wrongdoings and harbour moral emotions to suffer such mistreatment. Considering interspecies performance, this is a form of entertainment where a human consciously decides to perform alongside a nonhuman. The human theatre-maker has made the nonhumans' decision for them. Since nonhumans lack the moral agency to refuse to be involved in interspecies performance, they are then exploited when they are the receiver of any immoral treatment in the performative space.

Additionally, Kagan's notion of "modal personism" and this idea of being rational and self-conscious could also be misinterpreted, as it leaves room for personal opinion and judgment. Considering an example of one creating interspecies performance, this theatre-maker could be a bad person, perhaps convicted of a crime, yet because of their species line, they are a "modal" person capable of being rational and self-conscious. An animal involved in interspecies performance could exist and not commit anything that would be perceived as "bad", but because of their species and lack of "person", they are subjected to discrimination and exploited to perform. Kagan is not denying that animals are moral beings; rather, they are less morally relevant in comparison to humans.

As a conclusion to avoid careless animal representation in performance, Robert Garner (2018) brings forward Jeremy Bentham's understanding where, "the question" of moral status is not "Can they reason? Nor, Can they talk? But, Can they suffer?" (p. 320). Suppose there is a general understanding that a nonhuman animal is aware of any unjust treatment and discrimination it endures as a moral patient that harbours moral emotions. In that case, speciesism challenges individuals to be conscious of the unwritten morality of relations they share with animals; the moral patient's posthuman framework suggests blurring the line of distinction between. Highlighting speciesism stresses that in a performance context, theatre-makers have a responsibility to challenge this by ensuring that how an animal is represented on stage employs a morality of relations that sets aside any personal prejudice towards the nonhuman agent. Now, I introduce the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker and spectator to examine how this challenging of speciesism can be achieved

through adhering to a poetics that questions anthropocentrism, thus comprehending how an animal can be represented ethically on stage as this co-performing agent.

Chapter Three

Animal Poetics: The Humanity of Contemporary Interspecies

Performance-Making

In the following section, I engage with poetics to understand how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer. The first section introduces the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker and spectator when paying attention to animals on stage. Animals are part of Performance studies, where this section contemplates “good” ethical decision-making regarding nonhuman lives in performance. The importance of recognising animal agency is also highlighted in this section to comprehend how interspecies performance can be carried out ethically, ensuring the ‘performing animal’ is protected in the creative space as an equal co-performer.

I lead into theatre-making and engaging with poetics to challenge anthropocentrism, where I engage with Aristotle’s notion of ‘how’, within poetics. This aims to uncover how theatre-makers can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer through their interspecies performance work. I introduce Critical Animal Studies (CAS) within Performance studies to challenge anthropocentrism and elevate the animal beyond representation as a sign system, urging that the animal should be portrayed as an equal agent to the human counterpart, rather than a metaphor or prop.

Concluding this chapter, I introduce spectatorship, detailing the influence the “animal turn” had on CAS to comprehend an animal’s mode of existence and reject speciesism. I highlight the ethics of spectatorship where audience members are encouraged to perceive performance from a nonhuman perspective as a means to reject speciesism, ensuring the nonhuman is cared for morally within the creative space. I suggest that the way an animal is represented on stage emotionally moves spectators through affect, where witnessing a nonhuman in performance is influential in challenging the ethical implications within the human-animal relationship.

Ethics of Attentiveness: Theatre-Making & Spectatorship

To consider how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer, the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker and spectator play a crucial role in understanding how to view the nonhuman animal as such. To understand this ethics of attention, Cull Ó Maoilearca (2019) explains:

As Donna Haraway suggests, the etymology of seeing...invites consideration of the relationship between attention and respect: to taking care in an ethical sense and the careful, iterative act of observation that does not judge on first impressions, but considers others as worthy of re-spect, or a second look (p. n.p)

Cull Ó Maoilearca combines Haraway's notion of vision or sight with Amanda Boetzkes' 2010 understanding of "the fundamental ethical question" to argue whether this is a sensibility analysis of and for nonhuman animals or rather, 'if ethics is a matter of embodied behaviours improvised between actors within the uncertainty of specific contexts' to understand how practices within performance play a crucial role in determining ethical interspecies performance (ibid.).

Two bodies on stage, such as a human and a nonhuman, can create a locus of meaning-making. Specifically with spectatorship, there is an entitlement where one individual may position themselves against nonhuman animals to navigate social and cultural beliefs that suggest the status of nonhuman animals should be questioned. This questioning does not apply to the human animal counterpart in the performative space. Therefore, for the animal to be viewed as a co-performer, attention must be paid to the nonhuman in this ethics of attentiveness. Acknowledging the nonhuman as a sentient, moral patient that exceeds representation as a prop, sign, or symbol enables the animal, something that lacks agency, to gain agency as a co-performer.

The ethics of paying attention as a theatre-maker and spectator come from considering how the animal gains agency to become a co-performer, introducing a nexus of ethical performance-making and spectatorship. Interspecies performance-making can be created to represent animals ethically as co-performers when one acknowledges that nonhumans matter morally, thereby influencing right and wrong decision-making regarding the animal. Aristotle's *Nicomachean Ethics*, originating over 2,300 years ago, toys with ideas such as 'what's good and how do I be that? That's what the subject of ethics is about' (Hillside College, 2009, 01:18). If ethics is

a philosophical framework used for identifying morally what humans should do, 'I argue that ethics is the study of how best to live...learning how to be good and that is the whole question' (ibid., 02:18-04:30). The premise of being "good" and therefore acting in a way that is considered morally right is identified in the first chapter and page of *Nicomachean Ethics* where 'Every art and every inquiry, and similarly every action as well as choice, is held to aim at some good. Hence people have nobly declared that the good is that at which all things aim' (Bartlett and Collins, 2011, p. 1).

Considering interspecies performance as a type of art, the choices made by a theatre-maker regarding how the nonhuman animal is represented in the creative space can define their "goodness" as a human being. Understanding the aim of being good comes with acknowledging the presence of nonhuman animals within Schechner's "broad-spectrum" approach of Performance studies as a means to do right by the animal, where he first highlighted the performative behaviour of primates before introducing animals as a species group into the realm of performance in his 1977 book *Performance Theory*.

The notion of making good, moral choices regarding an animal is a crucial practice for theatre-makers to understand how they represent the nonhuman animal ethically on stage. Animals as a topic of concern in the study of performance highlights that attention has been paid to nonhuman rights and welfare in this ethics of attentiveness. Performance studies adhere to the fact that:

The animal liberation, advocacy, and rights movements have emerged out of ideas, theories, and actions based upon the seemingly simple, but profoundly radical, premise that nonhuman animals are subjects with agency, not objects to be used as humans see fit (Nocella II, Sorenson, Socha and Matsu, 2014, p. 19).

An ethics of attentiveness pays attention to the moral standing of the nonhuman within Performance studies and challenges speciesist attitudes that 'scorned concern for nonhumans as a waste of time and resources that would be better used to help humanity' (ibid., 20). Ultimately, good decision-making, aimed at ethically depicting the nonhuman as a co-performer within interspecies performance, challenges the prejudice and dismissal of animal rights or welfare within speciesism, as ethical animal representation on stage cannot be achieved if the nonhuman is portrayed as a resource to the human rather than an equal agent and collaborator.

Theatre-Making: Engaging with Poetics as a Means to Challenge Anthropocentrism

To understand how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer, Aristotle's notion of 'how' within poetics aids in comprehending this. Matthew James Smith (2025) reveals, 'In modern phenomenological and cultural writing, poetics is treated as an instrument for thinking about modes of being that are hidden in the ordinary ways things are described (p. n.p). Poetics can aid in understanding how things are put together, how one achieves things, how one discusses those and how one analyses them as 'an "ontological amplification" of phenomena' (ibid.). Furthermore, poetics provides insight into how one understands something based on the premise of a reality or thing that already exists, which enables one to consider how an animal can be represented as a co-performer abiding by existing rights and regulations concerning the well-being of nonhuman animals.

As a theatre-maker, understanding how to ethically represent an animal as a co-performer on stage can be achieved by respecting existing animal welfare acts that aim to improve humans' treatment of nonhumans in systems such as the entertainment industry. According to the UK's largest animal charity, RSPCA, an animal in entertainment is referred to as a 'performing animal', where their website states:

By 'performing animal' we mean any animal taken away from their usual home environment or social group or who has been trained or set up to behave in a particular way for a production. This can be anything from simply sitting in one place to performing a complex sequence of behaviours (no date, p. n.p.).

There are laws in place to conserve the safety and well-being of 'performing animals', as the notion that they can be trained or instructed to act in a performative way hints at the agency they possess as a species. If a nonhuman is required to act a certain way for a theatre-maker's performance, 'Under the Animal Welfare Act 2006, which applies in England and Wales, those responsible for an animal have a duty of care to provide for the animal's needs' (p. n.p). Ultimately, interspecies performance is not illegal or a type of art that should be shunned, as laws are in place to protect the livelihood of nonhuman animals. It is when these regulations are disregarded that ethical implications arise within this type of performance-making.

As a theatre-maker incorporating a nonhuman into their work, animal rights and liberation movements must not be ignored. These regulations are developed on the premise that nonhuman animals are agents and participants in their environment, including the performance space, and not some disposable 'other'. Therefore, engaging with poetics to identify how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer provides an insight into how the animal gains agency to do so.

Performance creates a space to interrogate the human-animal relationship, where the interdisciplinary field of study, CAS, holds space within Performance studies to challenge anthropocentrism. From here, one can understand how the nonhuman can be represented on stage as a co-performer. Nocella II, Sorenson, Socha and Matsu (2014) state:

CAS developed to challenge two specific fields of theory: (1) Animal Studies (AS), rooted in vivisection and animal testing in the hard sciences and (2) HAS, which reinforces the socially constituted human-animal binary through which detached scholars look at animals as objects without agency that exist to be theoretically studied and examined (p. 23).

CAS ensures the animal, similarly to the human, is acknowledged for its agency rather than its species, where one may comprehend nonhumans as objects to be acted upon, incapable of acting for themselves. Blurring the line of distinction between humans and animals within the realm of performance enables CAS to challenge how humans distinguish themselves from animals. From here, the human perspective is questioned, avoiding anthropocentric performance-making approaches. Considering the ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker, CAS critiques portrayals on stage that are developed from an anthropocentric perspective, thus disregarding the moral significance of the nonhuman counterpart. Engaging with poetics and the notion of how an animal is represented as a co-performer stems from challenging anthropocentrism.

It is evident that to understand how to ethically represent an animal as a co-performer is to acknowledge they are included in Performance studies since 'nonhuman animals are subjects with agency' (ibid., 19). John Berger's 1977 essay *Why Look at Animals?* provides useful insight into anthropocentric portrayals of nonhuman animals in written text, scripts or literature, which can later be challenged. Jonathon Burt (2005) close-reads Berger's work, stating:

In the period prior to the nineteenth century, he argues, animals are, in addition to their uses as human resources, mapped onto a language of signs. They are “messengers”, “promises”, the “first metaphor”, the “first symbols”, they “offered explanations” (p. 207).

Berger’s essay suggests that non-human animals have not always been regarded as agents, an idea that remains subject to debate among some individuals today.

Morten Tønnessen and Kadri Tüür (2014) elaborate, stating ‘In a cultural context, the manner in which we represent animals says a lot about who we are, or who we strive to be, and what we are conflicted about’ (p. 1). On stage, if an animal is used as a sign, metaphor or symbol, a speciesist performance-making approach is applied as the nonhuman is alienated from its human counterpart; the animal is ‘read’ on stage as a representation of something other than itself, an agent.

How a nonhuman is ‘read’ on stage could influence how the animal is then represented as a co-performer. Grounding this briefly in semiotics, Tønnessen and Tüür (2014) reveal:

The term ‘representation’ can be regarded as a general notion as well as a semiotic term...The scholarly field of semiotics is a fitting overall perspective for the study of animal representations because it deals with the world in terms of meaning and significance (ibid., 4).

Placing an animal on stage as a performer creates meaning-making in a way a human actor never could. There is an unreliability in the animal as a sign system, which allows for greater discrepancy and uncertainty in meaning. If the animal is in a position to be ‘read’ or interpreted, then the notion of viewing the nonhuman animal as a co-performer may be unachievable. It is unfair if the animal is ‘read’ on stage when the human is not. Within Performance studies, CAS challenges anthropocentric notions that reduce animals to these systems as:

CAS is not only opposed to the physical exploitation, torture, and murder of nonhuman animals by scientists, but it also is strongly opposed to the theoretical analytical dissection of nonhuman animals, which is not concerned with their oppression (Nocella II, Sorenson, Socha and Matsu, 2014, p. 24).

If the animal is represented on stage as a sign system, any regulations established to protect the well-being of the nonhuman animal could be disregarded. To elaborate, on stage audiences are confronted with the iconic value of the nonhuman, where the animal can serve as a tool to challenge ethics, anthropocentrism or speciesism. In performance, a human actor is not the role they play; however, the dog is the dog, or the pig is the pig, meaning spectators are confronted by the real animal rather than

the representational. The ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker plays a crucial role in engaging with poetics to ensure the animal is not 'read' on stage for something other than itself, thus achieving ethical representation of the nonhuman as a co-performer.

Spectatorship: The “Animal Turn” as a Means to Reject Speciesism

Amid animal discourse, humankind assumes they are the bearers of knowledge regarding nonhuman livelihoods and welfare, where:

the ways in which human society deals with its co-existence with animals, and the ways it interacts with, uses, and handles them are complex and embedded in paradoxes...thus, the human-animal relationship is not an innocent one (Andersson, Björck, Jennbert and Lönngren, 2014, p. 5).

Human animals have mapped nonhuman animals onto anthropocentric domains to understand the complexity within this relationship and the ethical implications that arise when interacting with this ‘other’. Above all else, animals are living beings with feelings, emphasising ‘the animals we study are never reducible to research objects’, or even objects of performance (ibid.,13). It is the very notion of ‘the human’ setting itself apart from ‘the animal’, this ‘other’, that exposes the nonhuman to speciesist attitudes and a difference in treatment due to the distinction in species.

Reintroducing regulations in place for the protection of nonhuman lives, Mansi Gupta (2021) explains:

While animal welfare is increasingly protected in domestic jurisdiction, animal rights are still hardly recognized, although they would serve animals better. Animal rights needs to be universalized in order to deploy effects in global setting (p. 1132-1133.).

Unfortunately, animal rights and welfare do not hold enough moral significance universally to serve animals in the way they are intended. To challenge speciesism and this dismissal of animal rights, ‘CAS promotes justice for all animals and challenges the socially constructed dominant relationship between humans and nonhuman animals’ (Nocella II, Sorenson, Socha and Matsu, 2014, p. 26). In the field of Performance studies, CAS was influenced by significant recognition of the “animal turn”. To reject speciesism, the “animal turn” within Performance studies enables the realm of performance to interrogate the human-animal relationship by analysing the poetics of how humans represent and depict animals in industries such as television, film and theatre.

Human dominance and anthropocentrism can then be challenged here to establish:

The “animal turn,” thus, brings along an alternative outlook on knowledge production that does not only include animals, but places them centre stage as key actors in the

innumerable modes of being in, and making sense of, the world (Andersson, Björck, Jennbert and Lönngren, 2014, p. 6).

Within the “animal turn”, the human perspective is cast aside to focus on that of the animal. Reintroducing poetics, as part of an “animal turn”, how the animal is represented on stage is key in understanding an animal mode of being in the world. For a spectator to comprehend the animal on stage as a co-performer, how the animal is represented is influenced by the theatre-maker to determine how the animal is ‘read’ on stage. It is evident to spectators whether the animal on stage has been represented as a mere object or a collaborative agent, where the theatre-maker has either complied with a high moral standard that supports existing welfare regulations that protect the performing animal or not.

Within Performance studies, the “animal turn” raises questions considering this ethics of attentiveness as a spectator, posing ‘If humans could perceive the world from the animals' point of view, would this change how humans perceive animals and, in turn, how they behave towards them?’ (Cull Ó Maoilearca, 2019, p. n.p). Through performance, the simple viewing of an animal on stage evokes heightened emotions and feelings from individuals. As a spectator, one can witness an animal on stage and attempt to place oneself in the position of the nonhuman to challenge their relationship with animals, raising possible ethical implications regarding how the performing animal has been represented on stage.

Carmen Faye Mathes (2021) highlights Peta Tait’s definition of ‘affect’ aimed at theatre and performance studies scholars, explaining ‘Emotion offers scholarly, sustained definitions of four key terms—the emotions, emotional feelings, affect, and mood’ (p. 3). Considering the earlier notion of interspecies performance-making that engages with poetics to understand how to represent the nonhuman beyond sign systems is key in enabling affect to take place; the performing animal on stage, if perceived as a sentient moral subject capable of co-performing, evokes spectators to be emotionally affected by this agent's presence on stage.

This feeling of co-performance between a human and a non-human depends on how the theatre-maker represents the animal on stage and how the spectator then interprets this. Here, a nexus of ethical performance-making and spectatorship is formed, as Faye Mathes (2022) reveals:

As Tait explains, affect studies concepts offer theatre-makers (from writers to directors, performers, musicians, technicians, and designers) the chance to explore how emotions, affects, or moods can be created on stage; 'The arousal of audience feeling is a theatrical intention', after all (ibid., 3-4).

As a maker of interspecies performance, you have the creative control to expose spectators to nonhuman animals in an intimate environment that differs from any other form of live art, and I will highlight how Kira O'Reilly does so in Chapter Four. As previously mentioned, the intent behind certain theatre-makers' interspecies creative work may be to enlighten audiences on the ethical implications associated with humans' treatment of non-humans within the meat and entertainment industries, for example. Ultimately, for the audience to truly acknowledge the animal on stage and question their relationship to nonhumans within said industries, they must 'bear witness' to the animal in this performative setting to be affected as part of an ethics of attentiveness.

The Save Movement (TSM) are a global animal rights organisation with over 200 Save groups. I introduce TSM as an example of this ethics of attentiveness as a spectator, where at the gates of the slaughterhouse, individuals are exposed to the mass of farm animals that are transported for slaughter in this act of 'bearing witness' to the nonhuman (Katsouraki, 2019, p. 289). Such a vulnerable, shared space between individuals could replicate that of a theatre, where the vulnerability of the animal in an exploitative environment affects spectators. Katsouraki (2019) clarifies, 'And yet, it is more than witnessing but a sort of active interaction that unfolds as a deep, profound sharing of oneself in *being present* at the affliction of an-*other*' (ibid.). TSM encourages spectators to place themselves in the position of the animal, this 'other' in an ethics of attentiveness similar to spectating an animal in a theatrical setting, creating an 'ethical provocation' of recognising what it would feel like to be killed as a means to restore pain in the animal (ibid.).

Chapter Three has combined poetics and the "animal turn" to understand how an animal is 'read' on stage through the act of bearing witness, which not only affects a rejection of speciesism amongst spectators but encourages a poetics of interspecies performance-making that pays attention to existing animal ethics in an ethics of attentiveness regarding how the animal is read on stage. Conclusively, perceiving performance from an animal's perspective enables the nonhuman to purge spectators of profound feelings, where affect encourages ethical concern to be

raised regarding the morality of how contemporary interspecies performance can ethically represent an animal as a co-performer. Chapter Four shall now introduce O'Reilly as a representative example of how she achieves this portrayal of a nonhuman within her practice.

Chapter Four

What's On Stage: Approaches to Contemporary Interspecies

Performance-Making

I will now analyse two of Irish artist Kira O'Reilly's interspecies performance works to explore the ethics of performance. I first highlight O'Reilly's creative practice and approaches within her interspecies work to showcase the ethical dimension that is prominent within her practice. Specifically, I will be analysing O'Reilly's *inthewrongplaceness* (2005) and *Falling Asleep With a Pig (FAWaP)* (2009). I have selected these two pieces of interspecies performance because they highlight the key points of my theoretical investigation regarding much of the current interspecies poetics in terms of animal ethics and the use or representation of animals on stage.

Inthewrongplaceness is a one-to-one performance between O'Reilly and a pig cadaver, where audience members are invited into the creative space to move either of the bodies through manipulative touch. Affect is created throughout this piece as topics such as animal research and animal lab practices are highlighted. O'Reilly's *FAWaP* features her and Deliah, a pot-bellied pig, sharing a pig pen within a gallery exhibition. Both bodies in the space share similar universal habits such as eating, breathing and sleeping, highlighting a likeness between humans and nonhumans and erasing the notion of 'otherness' between the two bodies in the space.

Despite these interspecies performance works taking to the stage from 2005 to 2011, the relevance and topics addressed within each piece have only grown more acute. Through analysing O'Reilly's background and her work, I can depict how she transforms the status of the pig she is working with to an equal co-performer, where the animal meets the threshold of co-creator. The selection of O'Reilly's work I am analysing draws upon pigs specifically as the animal co-performer. I detail her familiarity with pigs to indicate an engagement with poetics and the notion of adhering to existing animal rights throughout her work, all to highlight how she ethically represents a nonhuman, specifically a pig, as a co-performer.

Kira O'Reilly's Creative Practice & Approach

UK-based performance artist Kira O'Reilly began as a blood artist, working in the contexts of live art. Following her blood work, O'Reilly transitioned into bio-performance, developing live art pieces with animals (kirao'reilly.com, no date, p. n.p). The driving force of her live creative work typically focuses on the human-animal relationship, engaging with themes of ecology, which is the study of living things and their relationship with their environment. O'Reilly's live art 'often involves the cutting of her skin, and recent pieces have also involved animals, including leeches and pigs' (Dodington, 2009, p. n.p), where her interspecies performance work challenges the morality or relations between humans and animals, specifically humans' treatment of nonhumans.

Considering the presence of animals within the entertainment, meat or science industries, O'Reilly highlights the moral wrongdoings nonhumans endure in such industries on stage throughout her live art. Through considering existing animal rights and welfare acts devised to protect nonhuman well-being, O'Reilly engages with nonhumans to make performative nods throughout her work to animal exploitation, scientific experimentation or the slaughtering process. As a theatre-maker of interspecies performance, in this ethics of attentiveness, O'Reilly is conscious of existing rights that protect her performing animal, as she is aware that the nonhuman lacks the agency to refuse to co-perform alongside her. An ethical dimension is created here, where O'Reilly reveals in an interview with visual artist Liucija Dervinytė (2022) that 'There is always an acknowledgement of death or suffering and that the species, whatever that is, don't give any kind of consent, there is no agreement, no approval of that' (p. n.p).

O'Reilly does not dismiss the ethical implications present in her interspecies work, as she often highlights the morality of relations between humans and animals through interacting in what would be perceived as controversial interspecies engagement. Here, O'Reilly's work can be problematised, where, despite drawing on the use of a pig as a co-creator to depict an abandonment of humanity's implied moral responsibility to nonhumans, O'Reilly imposes a natural being into an unnatural setting that it cannot consent to performing in.

To not dismiss the ethical implications within her work, O'Reilly draws on ethics as a poetics; addressing this practice in itself is problematic, whilst simultaneously creating a performative space to interrogate the human-animal relationship and challenge how a nonhuman animal can be represented on stage. Later in her 2022 interview, Dervinyté posed O'Reilly with the question, 'since you often work with other life forms, what ethical issues do you find and how do you address them within your practice?' to which O'Reilly answered:

I worked with biopsied skin taken from the bodies of pigs used in bio-scientific research. As is the case with animal models, they stand in for a generic human body, hence the pigs stood in for my body. My idea was to eventually work with my own body, but this did not work out in the end. This instrumentalisation of another's body was part of the ethical relationship (p. n.p).

O'Reilly addresses that featuring a pig in her interspecies work, whether a live body (*FAWaP*) or a carcass (*Inthewrongplaceness*), was to blur the line of human-animal distinction. O'Reilly used the body of a pig as a stand-in for her own, showcasing the simplicity of two bodies in the creative space as co-performers. Within both interspecies performances, O'Reilly's body mimics that of a live pig and then a pig cadaver, thus erasing the notion of animal 'otherness'.

By not 'othering' herself from either pig in her work, O'Reilly elevates the nonhuman beyond representation as a sign system, helping one to think about the animal in terms of its morality. As a result, live audiences can perceive that the pig is nonhuman, but determine the animal as simply an equal body on the stage. Additionally, manipulating the nonhuman's body (a pig) as a tool, the way she would herself, meant O'Reilly could gauge the ethical implications of doing so and conclude what would and would not work ethically within these human-animal interactions.

Moreover, pigs are the select nonhuman animal that O'Reilly commonly features in her work. Despite all nonhuman animals being sentient beings, 'pigs are highly social animals...They communicate through a variety of vocalisations and body language, and they engage in complex social interactions' (Enviroliteracy Team, 2025, p. n.p). There are clear anatomical and physiological similarities between pigs and humans, as both species foster comparative emotional capacities (ibid.). This likeness between pigs and humans is to such an extent that when asked what drew her to work with them, O'Reilly responded:

So pigs and their presence, consumed and enmeshing with increased and more complexity with humans was and continues to be key. Their obvious intelligence, physiological similarity, embodiment of so many conflicting cultural values. (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 41).

When interviewed by Professors Bryndís Snæbjörnsdóttir and Mark Wilson in 2009, O'Reilly highlights the not-so-distinctive physical and mental traits between humans and pigs. Within this human-animal relationship, O'Reilly understands the likeness between the two species, thus erasing the notion of 'otherness' between herself and a pig by blurring the human-animal distinction. As part of an ethics of attentiveness, this creative approach could encourage theatre-makers to embrace the animality of their nonhuman animal partner. To do so, one may remove their status (which is deemed superior as they are human) over the animal, thus handing the nonhuman the agency to co-perform.

For a theatre-maker to acknowledge an animal as an agent within the creative space, posthumanism adheres to understanding this 'other'. Dervinyté (2022) had first asked O'Reilly 'How do you see the current state of ecology, and how do you address it in your art practice?' to which O'Reilly replied:

One of the hardest things to acknowledge is chaos and the unknown: uncertainty. I think that is where artistic practices can be of most value, as ways of being with uncertainty, and to an extent trying to locate oneself and viewers within it (p. n.p).

Ecology can aid humanity's understanding of the connection between humans, animals, organisms and plants to the Earth they inhabit. Not only are posthuman notions that suggest all living things are significantly related to one another addressed within ecology, but 'otherness' is erased as a result. Ecology provides insight into the relationship and interactions between living (biotic) and non-living (abiotic) entities (Biology Simple, 2024, p. n.p), to which O'Reilly suggests that, rather than shying away from the unpredictability of such relationships, ecology can encourage individuals to question their positionality alongside other living organisms and understand this 'other' throughout the creative practice.

To conclude this overview of O'Reilly's creative approach, I shall highlight an additional ethical dimension within her interspecies work. This interest with pigs being incorporated into her creative practice stemmed from O'Reilly's curiosity about their lives 'and the obvious care that was involved in their wellbeing, as well as the complexity of the issue of animal experimentation' (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson,

2017, p. 40). O'Reilly's genuine curiosity about the livelihood of pigs and humanity's treatment of them is depicted within her creative practice of *Inthewrongplaceness* and *FAWaP* which 'emerged as responses to these animal research and lab processes on my return to the UK' (ibid., 41). As an emotionally complex species, pigs were not incorporated into O'Reilly's interspecies work for the sake of it; rather, there was an acknowledgement on her behalf of the likeness between herself and said species, whilst simultaneously utilising her position as a human to scrutinise her species' treatment of pigs in a morality of relations between humans and animals.

Kira O'Reilly's *Inthewrongplaceness*

Firstly, I will be analysing O'Reilly's *Inthewrongplaceness* (2009), which premiered in Penzance, Cornwall. I shall be tracing the refinement and evolution of this 16-year-old piece, highlighting animal ethics as a poetics that showcases topics of animal lab processes and animal testing made prominent through affect and the erasure of animal 'otherness' in an ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker. When interviewed, O'Reilly describes that:

Inthewrongplaceness came out of an intense period of research whilst I was an artist in resident at *SymbioticA*, the arts and science research laboratory at University of Western Australia, where I had been learning basic tissue culture techniques including creating primary cell culture of pig skin (ibid., 40).

The notion of touch and how this combines with sight to create 'a sensuous feedback of flesh, albeit through the latex or vinyl glove, of temperature, weight and texture' (ibid.) sparked O'Reilly's interspecies work with *Inthewrongplaceness*. For this stage performance to spotlight animal rights, O'Reilly decided to work with a pig that had endured the slaughtering process for human consumption as an ethical acknowledgement of this process that results in 1.2 billion animal deaths for meat, fish and poultry per year (Viva, 2024, p. n.p). O'Reilly discloses that there are 6 variations of *Inthewrongplaceness*, yet 'It is incredibly simple. The work is made with a female pig cadaver weighing approximately 48 kgs that has been slaughtered for food consumption, so the internal organs have been removed' (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 39).

Within this performance, audience members are welcomed into the space for 10 minutes at a time, and a written invitation informs participants that they can touch either of the bodies on stage throughout the performance, yet this is not a requirement. Before any of the two bodies in the creative space can be touched or manipulated by her participants, O'Reilly explains:

They are also given latex or vinyl gloves with which to do this and are told that they must spray ethanol on their gloves upon entering the room where I am...The latex and vinyl gloves are a reference to lab work and behaviours (ibid., 39-44).

O'Reilly wanted to replicate her time as a researcher at *SymbioticA* to mimic the immense sensory experience present in animal laboratories. O'Reilly's stage created a space to again highlight animal rights within select industries. To do so, O'Reilly replicated these lab processes within her work on *Inthewrongplaceness* by utilising

sanitary gloves, despite the set design depicting a bedroom and not necessarily a scientific setting. Within this intimate bedroom setting, anthropocentrism can be challenged to erase 'otherness' as O'Reilly places the bare body of a pig alongside that of herself in a familiar human environment. Inviting the pig into such an intimate setting creates a contrast with the invasive lab practices highlighted through the piece, where neither vulnerable body is exempt from the act of audience touch within the piece.

To depict what happens throughout the performance, O'Reilly bares all on the stage that she shares with a select pig cadaver. Her naked body coils with the pig corpse to embrace in what has been described as a 'crushing slow-dance with the carcass in her arms' (Daily Mail Reporter, 2006, p. n.p). As the pig is essentially a shell of itself, O'Reilly depicts the workings of *Inthewrongplaceness*, stating:

I move the pigs body, I lie on her, I hold her, I insert parts of me inside her through the abattoir cuts and cavities, I try and fail to mimic the positions of her. I reposition our bodies again and again in relation to one another (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 39).

O'Reilly showcases on stage the flesh of two bodies in their natural form, where the vulnerability of her bare skin mirrors the exposure in treatment that pigs endure daily. On stage, the pig could be 'read' by audiences as dead, which is the real rather than the representational portrayal of the nonhuman. Ethical implications arise here regarding animal morality, as it is difficult to read a pig cadaver on stage any differently than being deceased.

Here, there is something highly unnatural and constructed within the piece that stems from challenging how an animal is to be represented or 'read' on stage. Within this specific example of a human-animal relationship, O'Reilly's naked body posing in the performative space, thus being a bedroom, hints at sexual connotations through the 'supposed intimacy' she shares with the pig carcass on stage (ibid., 44). O'Reilly attempts to replicate the moral status of the cadaver as closely as she can, ensuring her body is exposed and subject to manipulative touch. Perhaps representing the animal in a sensual light associated with human lust was a means for O'Reilly to challenge the extremities of animal representation on stage. Here, alterity can be embraced to question the portrayal of nonhuman animals in certain human domains, challenging how this is carried out in a morality of relation.

Within the intimate bedroom setting captured by O'Reilly, she does not dismiss the backlash that representation of a pig in such a light will raise; O'Reilly explains, 'I am well aware of the controversy this performance will create' (Daily Mail Reporter, 2006, p. n.p). As a theatre-maker, O'Reilly is aware of more severe concerns regarding control and power that can arise alongside the intended tenderness and care within this human-animal interaction. However, to highlight the thoughtfulness of the nonhuman animal involved within *Inthewrongplaceness*, O'Reilly explains, 'I do not think of the moving of the body of the pig as manipulation – of course it is but I embrace, hold, carry, and lie on, under and in the body' (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 44).

Once word got out regarding O'Reilly's interspecies work on *Inthewrongplaceness*, critics latched on to the notion that the pig cadaver in the creative space was subjected to manipulation, dominance and control. O'Reilly used a dead pig as a stand-in for her own body, illustrating to audiences the ease with which a nonhuman body replicates a human body. Considering CAS as part of a performance context that challenges performance-making for a human perspective, O'Reilly positioned herself alongside a pig cadaver to erase animal 'otherness' and locate herself within the chaos of this relationship. O'Reilly was able to do so by engaging with the earlier notion of the unpredictability within ecology, such as the relationship between biotic and abiotic beings.

Even so, misinformation regarding the nature of *Inthewrongplaceness* resulted in the reputation of the piece being tarnished, where O'Reilly reveals:

Hence a very different kind of work was speculated on and the opportunities to create a meaningful public discussion on ethics, care and relation was lost for quick newspaper selling and a knee-jerk reaction (ibid., 41).

Regardless of numerous critics' opinions, *Inthewrongplaceness* was intended to spark such discussions as O'Reilly reveals above. O'Reilly sought to highlight animal ethics through the artistic choice of challenging anthropocentrism by removing her agency and subjecting her body to manipulation through human touch, similar to the pig cadaver. Moreover, care was taken to highlight the simplicity of controlling either body on stage, where O'Reilly could also showcase the similarities within the human-animal relationship (Dervinytė, 2022, p. n.p).

Despite Cary Wolfe's understanding of 'the human' and 'the animal' as two beings that encounter being on the same Earth very differently from one another, as stated in Chapter One, Ryan C.P. Fics (2025) states:

At bottom, all scientific discourses, all thinkers in the Western tradition, have not provided a sufficient account for the differentiation of beings from Being, and for the difference of "the human" from "the animal." (p. 100)

Erasing the human-animal distinction and understanding the likeness between herself and a pig carcass curated an ethical angle to O'Reilly's interspecies performance-making approach within *Inthewrongplaceness*. O'Reilly is a human being who cannot comprehend an animal mode of *being* in the world. However, as an interspecies performance-maker in an ethics of attentiveness, she has a bond of responsibility to her performing animal to establish a morality within this relationship by removing her agency as a human performer and ethically comprehending her positionality beside a dead pig.

To cater to an ethological creative process, O'Reilly asked herself essential ethical questions, such as:

How and where do I position myself in relation to these power chains, and how do I begin to navigate and negotiate them in relation to these animals I am working from/on/with/about?' (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 47).

To embrace the uncertainty of collaborating with a pig within *Inthewrongplaceness*, O'Reilly utilised a posthuman framework to erase the distinction between the human and animal within this ecological relationship, all whilst not dismissing her position of power as a human interspecies performance-maker. As depicted in Chapter Two, status amongst species is erased due to the posthuman notion that suggests every living organism shares a relationship, connecting them ancestrally. Encouraged by notions rooted in CAS, O'Reilly positioned herself against a pig cadaver to challenge anthropocentrism through removing herself of agency and stripping herself of status, enabling her to blur the distinction between humans and animals to depict two equal subjects on stage.

To comprehend this representation, Giorgio Agamben's depictions of life, *Zoe* and *bios*, stated in Chapter Two, aid in understanding how O'Reilly subjects herself to the status of a pig cadaver within *Inthewrongplaceness*. Contrasting with *bios*, individuals who are entitled to power, O'Reilly would be considered a *Zoe* because

she is female; similarly to the pig that is a *Zoe* due to its animality. O'Reilly used a pig cadaver as a representation of herself, where Katsouraki (2017) explains:

First, that the ways in which the interface between animals and posthuman representation are enacted in and through contemporary bio/interspecies performance *replaces* the notion of '*bios*,' which is attributed to civic life, or the life of the citizen, with the more visceral and vulnerable modality of life as '*zoe*' (p. 74).

Within interspecies performance, the notion of *bios* can be eliminated to erase any notion of status amongst performers. *Zoe* is a basic way of existing that O'Reilly depicts through representing herself and a pig carcass *being* vulnerable on stage and subjected to audience manipulation. Even if the pig within *Inthewrongplaceness* were alive, it would still be considered a *Zoe* because of its species.

To remove the concept of *bios*, 'In a theatrical context, '*bios*' could be understood as 'playing' fictional characters and embodying the actions of the discursive, social and political life' (ibid.). *Bios* in this context could be acting out a role of portraying human-centred perspectives and depicting their experiences; however, interspecies performance can stray from human focus, enabling humans to represent nonhumans. Katsouraki (2017) elaborates by stating '*Zoe*, on the other hand, could stand for what both curtails and transcends the life of *bios* or biopolitical life, as the basic essence of all life is first and foremost as *Zoe*' (ibid.).

Zoe is shared amongst all living organisms as it equates to simply being alive. O'Reilly features a dead pig within *Inthewrongplaceness*, yet this pig was once a live *Zoe*, enabling posthuman notions to depict two equal species on stage with little power for audiences to overpower and manipulate. O'Reilly's bare and naked body represents the pig cadaver, who is a stand-in and mimic of her. Katsouraki (2017) elaborates by stating:

In such stagings of human and nonhuman vitality, *zoe* designates the indispensable, uncontaminated life force that following Jane Bennett's understanding of 'the vibrant matter' (2010) is *shared* between both human animals and non-human animals. This moves towards a radically post or non-anthropocentric approach to live performance that I will call *Zoedramatics* – that is, the dramatization of *zoe* as a modality of affective experience and representation (ibid., 74-75).

Katsouraki's term *Zoedramatics* aids in understanding the poetics of how Kira O'Reilly represented a nonhuman animal on stage, simultaneously as it depicted her own body. Jane Bennett's work on *Vibrant Matter* (2009) sparks notions such as 'Because when we focus on what something *is*, we separate it from what it *could be*'

(Montgomery, 2013, p. n.p), where, despite the pig featured within *Inthewrongplaceness* being dead, we cannot comprehend it *being* anything other than its physical state. Alternatively, O'Reilly is a live female whose appearance cannot realistically mimic that of a pig's carcass. Ultimately central in Wolfe's understanding of 'the human' and 'the animal', each being cannot replicate or understand the other's mode of existence.

Nevertheless, this shared notion between humans and nonhumans, where they can be something they are not, sparks a non-anthropocentric approach that moves away from radically human-centred interspecies performance-making angles. Conclusively, *Inthewrongplaceness* combines ethics, care and relation to erase human status and instead represent two beings that harbour similar mental and physical capacities co-performing in a performative space.

Kira O'Reilly's *Falling Asleep With a Pig (FAWaP)*

Debuting in 2009, a few years after *Inthewrongplaceness*, O'Reilly's *FAWaP* is a further example of interspecies performance that highlights the findings of my theoretical investigation into animal ethics, specifically on stage. Contrasting with her previous practice, O'Reilly explains that:

Falling asleep with a pig creates a situation where a human animal (myself) and a non human animal (a pig, specifically Deliah, a Vietnamese Potbellied pig) share a specially designed and constructed dwelling for 36 hours (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 39).

Throughout the duration of *FAWaP*, O'Reilly and her live performing animal, Deliah, share a pig pen with an indoor and outdoor enclosure, whilst audience members freely manoeuvre around the space and observe either of the animals. Blurring the distinction and notion of 'otherness' between herself and a pig, this time a live one, O'Reilly remains inside what replicates a pig pen alongside Deliah at all times, ensuring she does not dictate or influence how the performance will unfold.

Within *Inthewrongplaceness*, O'Reilly's bare skin replicates the pig cadaver, as she embraces the nonhuman in her naked arms to perform an intimate slow-dance. Contrastingly, performing with the liveliness of Deliah in *FAWaP* invites imitation into the space. O'Reilly explains that the nature of the piece consists of the two bodies on stage being spectated to fall naturally in and out of sleep for 'the positioning of us, two entirely similar mammals, to be considered in this most basic and fundamental of states common to mammals' (ibid.). To highlight morality and ensure Deliah is not 'read' on stage as anything other than herself, O'Reilly showcases the simplicity of two differing species replicating one another as equal subjects with equal moral standing.

In both interspecies works, the pig is co-present with O'Reilly on stage and corporeal; however, Deliah is a living moral patient who possesses the agency to co-perform in a way that is limited to a pig cadaver. In this ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker, *FAWaP* follows a similar ethical approach to *Inthewrongplaceness*; the two participants are different and an 'other' to one another, yet they exceed their physical representation to become a construct one comes to know through talking about and understanding them (Farzand, 2023, p. n.p). Therefore, despite the more obvious representation of Deliah as a co-performer because she is alive, the basis of

O'Reilly's interspecies work is to blur the human-animal distinction, highlighting the simplicity of 'The idea of the two species, two bodies, and two individuals, entirely other, being discursive bodies' (ibid.).

How O'Reilly highlights this notion of 'discursive bodies' is through removing her human agency to highlight two beings on stage, rather than a woman and a pig, two entirely different species. To produce her interspecies performance-making from this ethically mindful approach, O'Reilly reveals her understanding of:

This includes everything from ideas of display, exhibition, living bodies as art works, power imbalances, consent, ethics to animal welfare, DEFRA rulings on the movement of animal live stock around the country, practices of containment and contagions, hazards and waste (Snæbjörnsdóttir and Wilson, 2017, p. 39).

FAWaP was inspired by the many ways in which humans utilise pigs for food and non-food resources. As part of a poetics of adhering to existing animal rights and welfare that touch on these sensitive issues associated with her nonhuman partner, O'Reilly put herself on display alongside Delilah. Here, O'Reilly encouraged an ethics of attentiveness amongst spectators through affect to raise ethical and consensual concerns for the animal within this interspecies interaction. To do so, there was a supposed ladder in the pig pen that some observers criticised as it created 'an implicit hierarchy between human and animal' (ibid.).

This sense of human superiority was not in O'Reilly's creative intentions, as she responded to these criticisms by explaining it was a platform, revealing 'I (O'Reilly) thought it a good idea as it allowed some clear space if Deliah was stressed or unhappy and visually suggested the idea of a bed' (ibid.). Although O'Reilly received backlash to the presumed notion of human hierarchy created by a raised platform, speciesism was unintentionally rejected in an ethics of attentiveness as a spectator. Here, observers were led to question the superior positioning of the human animal on the stage as affect took place, challenging how the animal was represented as a counterpart.

This hierarchical depiction between O'Reilly and Deliah was not entirely deliberate; rather, O'Reilly, with the help of Donna Haraway, created a ramp that welcomed space for the nonhuman animal to retreat to throughout the performance if needed. In an acknowledgement of highlighting animal rights and welfare for O'Reilly's performing animal on stage, Deliah was offered a safe place to remove

herself from the realm of performance. Here, O'Reilly stresses that this work sparked after observing pigs' everyday habits at the University of Western Australia and noting the obvious care they need. In a poetics of understanding ethical animal representation on stage, O'Reilly is aware of existing welfare regarding nonhuman lives through working closely with them. How O'Reilly does so stems from rejecting anthropocentrism to place herself alongside Deliah to engage in the familiar habit of drifting in and out of sleep in what has been described as 'Soft, sleepy, warm, cosy, two bodies at their most basic' to remove the notion of human hierarchy (ibid., 41).

Perhaps a way for O'Reilly to include Deliah in her work from an ethical approach and understand their relationship was not to require the pig to behave in a certain way, but instead position herself alongside Deliah to embrace the uncertainty within the relationship. Deliah might be a nonhuman animal, but this does not deprive her of the ability to perform; Dorothee Fischer (2020) states, 'Inter-species art proposes to lessen the opposition between human and non-human animals by acknowledging animals' undeniable artistic qualities and thereby stressing the need for rethinking traditional images of artistry' (p. 90). Thereby, O'Reilly did not hand Deliah a role but trusted that performance would emerge through the nonhuman's characteristics to curate *FAWaP*.

In an ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker, *FAWaP* is an intimate human-animal interaction that showcases two co-performers in their most simple state, acting as themselves in this artistic collaboration. Fischer (2020) explains:

Furthermore, the animals do not have to be trained to show specific behaviours that lead to art products. On the contrary, as Ullrich proposes, the aim is to let the animals work freely and embrace whatever emerges, to thereby give the creativity of the non-human contributor its own value. Thus, ideally, interspecies art emerges through respectful dialogue (ibid., 70).

This notion of 'respectful dialogue' within *FAWaP* stemmed from O'Reilly considering the posthuman notion of unlearning anthropocentrism to remove her status over Deliah. In a performance context, granting equal creative freedom to Deliah as an equal subject helped shape the piece and enabled O'Reilly to highlight animal morality through showcasing the likeness between a human and a nonhuman, thus blurring the distinction between humans and animals as she and a pig performed shared, universal habits.

If Deliah has creative freedom, she is entitled to ethical consideration as she is represented as a co-performer alongside O'Reilly. For O'Reilly to hand Deliah this creative control, she adheres to what Chapter Three highlights as Haraway's 'etymology of seeing' to see and pay attention to the ethics, care and relation of not judging, but respecting nonhuman life. *FAWaP* was created by observing the habits of pigs and then showcasing the morality of the animal on stage, thus respecting that, despite their species, they possess similar behaviours to humans. Arguably, O'Reilly therefore sees Deliah within this interspecies work, as there may be obvious physical differences between Deliah and herself, but this does not exceed the display of habitual likeness within the human-animal relationship.

As there is difficulty within speciesism and posthumanism to comprehend an animal with the same moral consideration as one would another human, O'Reilly is aware of this challenge in her interspecies work. At heart, O'Reilly is cautious of the unequal power balance within her interspecies work and therefore refrains from describing it as a form of 'collaboration' as she is aware that the pig cannot consent to performing, let alone collaborating (Dervinytė, 2022, p. n.p). In her 2022 interview, O'Reilly was asked about ethical issues within her work and how she approaches these. In a morality of relations to working specifically with a pig in *FAWaP*, O'Reilly replied:

A very large part of developing that piece was conversations with the producers of Arts Catalyst who were exemplary in this kind of expertise. For example, an expert on animal welfare was involved, who became an advisor for the piece (p. n.p).

Considering this implied bond of responsibility, O'Reilly and the on-set animal welfare advisor questioned human positionality within the gallery exhibition of the pig pen to prioritise Deliah's needs. Doing so identified any performative elements that could stress Deliah or make her unhappy to avoid causing the nonhuman any discomfort; however, O'Reilly is always conscious of animal suffering and a lack of consent that could result in death.

Furthermore, O'Reilly does not dismiss the ethical implications within her interspecies performance work as she simultaneously curates performances that depict to audiences that nonhuman animals are worthy of such consideration. As she does throughout *Inthewrongplaceness*, O'Reilly highlights to spectators in *FAWaP* how a pig's body can mimic her own, challenging morality and how to transition the

nonhuman patient into a subject that can co-perform; *Inthewrongplaceness* depicts a pig cadaver as a stand-in for a human body that can be manipulated as a mirror, contrasting with a human and a nonhuman that freely imitate one another in real time within *FAWaP*, all to erase the notion of 'otherness'.

Reintroducing Katsouraki's (2017) notion of *Zoedramatics* in a theatrical context where *Zoe* replaces *bios* to understand feelings, attitudes and depict representation, O'Reilly's interaction with Deliah adheres to posthuman notions that highlight human-animal likeness in their representative behaviours. Katsouraki (2017) elaborates, stating:

The dramatisation of *zoe* beyond the human asks us to rethink the placement of the animal in performance both creatively and relationally, provoking an ethics of attentiveness to what may be a forgotten human animality (p. 75).

Amplifying *Zoe* in an ethics of attentiveness means placing the animal within the realm of performance to challenge what makes a human, human and dismiss the distinction between humans and nonhumans that creates alterity or differences in treatment. I have demonstrated that within *FAWaP*, O'Reilly and Deliah represent one another; two bodies, two species, two beings. Therefore, to 'dramatise' *Zoe* in this context means to adhere to the posthuman relation between human-animal habits and behaviour in an ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker, meaning Deliah and O'Reilly represent one another to lead towards an appropriate level of ethical care being assigned to all beings in the creative space when it comes to the portrayal of one another on stage.

Conclusion

Conclusively, it is evident through a theoretical investigation of the ethics of animals on stage that the presence of nonhumans within Critical Animal Studies, Performance studies, and existing animal rights or welfare acts demonstrates that their morality is deserving of ethical consideration. Arguably, it is not enough to distinguish animals from humans based on their 'otherness', as 'othering' is present within the human-human relationship, which does not erase humanity of moral worth the way such a process does to nonhumans. Instead, I detail the deep-rooted connection between humans and animals, which aids in understanding how the implied morality of relations within scripture can take precedence over one's personal dislike for a nonhuman species as a result of rejecting speciesism.

Moreover, understanding Agamben's depictions of life, *Zoe* and *bios*, to elevate *Zoe* in the direction of non-anthropocentric approaches to live performance creates *Zoedramatics*, which assists an understanding in erasing the notion of superiority in human agency to enable all performers, humans and nonhuman, to be treated as co-creators of equal moral standing and thus represented as such on stage. Hence, you are left with an acknowledgement of posthumanism that challenges anthropocentrism by elevating the moral standing of the nonhuman to an equal subject that is represented ethically on stage.

Considering interspecies performance, there are moral implications associated with such art as the erasure of animal morality cannot be ignored, given that topics of consent, willing participation and refusal cannot be discussed between a human and nonhuman performer; however, I suggest that the very act of placing an animal on stage opposite a human enables the nonhuman to hone agency in the creative space as a co-creator, consequently allowing the animal to be 'read' as something that exceeds its species. Here, an understanding of how to erase 'otherness' is created through an ethics of attentiveness as a theatre-maker; a poetics of abiding by existing animal welfare acknowledges the animal on stage is not an object or prop, but still an animal who has different ethical needs, whilst simultaneously *seeing* the nonhuman as a performing animal who harbours the agency to co-perform.

Additionally, one can learn in an ethics of attentiveness as a spectator that bearing witness to an animal on stage challenges individuals to adopt an anti-speciesist attitude by comprehending interspecies performance from a nonhuman perspective. Here, the “animal turn” enables affect to profoundly move individuals to question the ethics of animal representation on stage, where performance helps one comprehend animal rights and the importance of adhering to such in a theatrical space when animal morality is taken into consideration to understand how the nonhuman should be portrayed ethically on stage.

Encapsulating my theoretical investigation of animal ethics into her work, Kira O'Reilly's practice demonstrates the importance of the ethics of attentiveness when making interspecies performance and then showcasing such work to a live audience. In a poetics of adhering to existing animal welfare, O'Reilly considers the role of animals in performance by treating the stage as a meeting ground that enables two bodies within two species groups to possess equal creative control through co-existing. Moral implications arise within interspecies performance when animal rights and welfare are dismissed; however, O'Reilly highlights how removing human agency as a theatre-maker can blur the distinction between humans and animals, thus setting an example of ethical nonhuman representation that adheres to a morality of relations.

O'Reilly does not claim that interspecies performance is some form of human-animal agreement or collaboration; rather, on stage, she enables her performing animal to *be*. Here:

In rooting ethical thought first and foremost in materiality and not in the rights of 'qualified' individuals, the distinctions between humans and animals, as far as ethical consideration is concerned, are erased (Pick, 2012, p. 80).

Erasing the human-animal distinction, such as 'otherness' between humans and animals, is a prominent approach throughout O'Reilly's interspecies practice as she challenges how the animal is read on stage through this removal of her own agency. Resultantly, the role of a pig cadaver in a piece such *Inthewrongplaceness* can mirror and replicate a human body, as the role of a live pig within a project such as *Falling Asleep With a Pig* can create liveliness and enable imitation between two bodies of differing species on stage. Therefore, conducting a theoretical investigation into the ethics of animals on stage and highlighting O'Reilly as a pioneer of this type

of work, the way an animal is ethically represented on stage as a co-performer stems from embracing animal morality to challenge anthropocentric performance-making. Here, doors open regarding how one develops or rethinks this poetics of abiding by existing animal welfare in the performative space to compose an established code of care for performing animals, thus ensuring that theatre-makers embrace animal 'otherness' and alterity all to move towards interspecies performance-making that is grounded in a morality of relations bonding humans to animals through their tacit moral responsibility, resulting in ethical representation of the animal on stage as a co-performer.

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